

Harnessing AI and Data-Intensive Technologies

Deliverable 2.6: Analysis of the AI and Data Regulatory Framework - Version 1

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Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AI Act	Artificial Intelligence Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689); also abbreviated AIA
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
BCP	Business Continuity Plan
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
CNIL	Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés (French data protection authority)
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary (W3C)
DGA	Data Governance Act
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DORA	Digital Operational Resilience Act
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DPV	Data Privacy Vocabulary
DSA	Digital Services Act
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
EHDS	European Health Data Space

Acronym	Definition
eIDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EUCC	EU Common Criteria-based Cybersecurity Certification Scheme
FRIA	Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPAI	General Purpose AI
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSAs	International Data Spaces Association
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
LIME	Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations
LLM	Large Language Model
MDR	Medical Devices Regulation
IVDR	In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation
ML	Machine Learning
NIS2	Network and Information Security Directive (Directive (EU) 2022/2555)
NIST	U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OWL	Web Ontology Language
QMS	Quality Management System
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RoPA	Records of Processing Activities
SBOM	Software Bill of Materials
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management

Acronym	Definition
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
TLPT	Threat-Led Penetration Testing
WP	Work Package

Table of Legislation

Term	Definition
Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act)	Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) [2024] OJ L 2024/1689
Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)	Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements (Cyber Resilience Act) [2024] OJ L 2024/2847
Data Act	Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act) [2023] OJ L 2023/2854
Data Governance Act (DGA)	Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance (Data Governance Act) [2022] OJ L 152/1
Digital Markets Act (DMA)	Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector (Digital Markets Act) [2022] OJ L 265/1
Digital Omnibus proposal	COM(2025) XXX final, European Commission, 2025
Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA)	Regulation (EU) 2022/2554 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on digital operational resilience for the financial sector [2022] OJ L 333/1
Digital Services Act (DSA)	Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market for Digital Services (Digital Services Act) [2022] OJ L 277/1
ePrivacy Directive	Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (ePrivacy Directive) [2002] OJ L 201/37

Term	Definition
European Electronic Communications Code (EECC)	Directive (EU) 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code [2018] OJ L 321/36
European Health Data Space Regulation (EHDS)	Regulation (EU) 2025/327 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 February 2025 on the European Health Data Space [2025] OJ L 2025/327
European Digital Identity Regulation (eIDAS 2.0)	Regulation (EU) 2024/1183 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 as regards establishing the European Digital Identity Framework [2024] OJ L 2024/1183
EU Cybersecurity Certification Scheme (EUCC)	Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2024/482 of 31 January 2024 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2019/881 as regards the adoption of the European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme (EUCC) [2024] OJ L 2024/482
Free Flow of Data Regulation	Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union. OJ L 303/59
General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation) [2016] OJ L 119/1
Interoperable Europe Act	Regulation (EU) 2024/903 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 March 2024 laying down measures for a high level of public sector interoperability across the Union [2024] OJ L 2024/903
Medical Devices Regulation / In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (MDR/IVDR)	Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR) [2017] OJ L 117/1; Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR) [2017] OJ L 117/176
NIS2 Directive	Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2 Directive) [2022] OJ L 333/80
Open Data Directive	Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information [2019] OJ L 172/56
Revised Product Liability Directive (rPLD)	Directive (EU) 2024/2853 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on liability for defective products (Revised Product Liability Directive) [2024] OJ L 2024/2853

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Context and Motivation

The European Union has built one of the world's most comprehensive regulatory frameworks for artificial intelligence and data-intensive technologies, comprising the AI Act, GDPR, Data Act, Data Governance Act, NIS2, the Cyber Resilience Act, DORA, the EHDS, and a dozen further instruments enacted over the past decade by different Directorates-General in response to different policy problems. Each instrument imposes obligations expressed in legal language — "appropriate technical and organisational measures", "meaningful human oversight", "state of the art" — that is deliberately abstract enough to remain adaptable as technology evolves, but that abstraction creates a substantial translation problem for the engineers, data architects, and researchers who must build systems that satisfy it.

Two sibling deliverables address adjacent parts of this problem. D1.1 maps the same regulatory landscape from a jurisprudential perspective, analysing how the law allocates actors, rights, obligations, and deterrence mechanisms across overlapping instruments. D2.2 surveys the existing compliance tools and methods built to operationalise these obligations. Deliverable D2.6 occupies the position between them: it analyses the regulatory framework with an engineer's reading rather than a lawyer's, asking not what the law says but what it requires of technical systems, and it does so across the full breadth of the in-scope instruments rather than the depth of a single article — that narrower, deeper task being the work of D2.4, which models AI Act Article 9 risk management requirements in semantic web form as a worked example of the kind of operationalisation D2.6 surveys at the level of the whole framework, and of D1.4, which develops the interdisciplinary formalisation framework for translating that same regulatory text into machine-readable legal knowledge.²

Key Contributions

This deliverable makes three primary contributions.

First, it provides a structured technical reading of the regulatory landscape, organised into a Data Regulatory Cluster and a Cybersecurity Regulatory Cluster, each further divided into sub-clusters that reflect genuine technical dependencies rather than legislative chronology. Within each cluster, obligations, prohibitions, permissions, and rights are translated into their engineering equivalents — design requirements, architectural constraints, access conditions, and service capabilities — using a consistent analytical vocabulary established in the document's theoretical foundations. The standards layer bridging legal text and technical implementation, including the presumption-of-conformity mechanism and the current state of harmonisation under JTC 21, CEN/CENELEC, and ENISA mandates, is mapped instrument by instrument, with gaps where no harmonised standard yet exists made explicit.

Second, the deliverable identifies and analyses the points of friction within this framework: regulatory interactions where obligations from different instruments overlap, conflict, or leave gaps, including the divergent incident-notification timelines under GDPR, NIS2, and DORA, and the double-conformity problem between the AI Act and the CRA. It maps the technical roles the framework creates — provider, deployer, controller, processor, data intermediary, essential entity, manufacturer — and the lifecycle dynamics that move actors between them, most consequentially the AI Act's deployer-to-provider reclassification triggers. It surveys the machine-readable vocabulary ecosystem that has emerged to represent these roles and obligations — DPV, ODRL, Croissant, AIRO, and related standards — and shows that while each component addresses a slice of the documentation problem, no integrated cross-regulation compliance substrate yet exists.

Third, the deliverable maps regulatory requirements onto the compliance-tooling landscape surveyed in D2.2, showing that tooling maturity is structurally uneven — deep for GDPR, nascent for the AI Act, thin for the Data Act and DGA — and identifies seven implementability gaps that are open research questions rather than engineering problems awaiting better software: explainability for deep models, machine unlearning, purpose limitation in federated data spaces, meaningful human oversight, software-and-model bills of materials, recommender transparency, and adversarial testing for general-purpose AI models with systemic risk. Four case studies — AI in high-risk healthcare and financial sectors, data spaces under the Data Act and EHDS, cybersecurity in critical infrastructure, and AI in education — ground this analysis in concrete deployment scenarios.

Practical Impact and Future Work

The analysis is intended as a structured reference point — a map that engineers, data architects, and researchers can use to identify which obligations apply to a given system, which standards and tools are available to satisfy them, and where the current state of the art falls short. The accompanying mapping tables are designed for direct reuse in compliance tooling and ontology development elsewhere in the project. Future work should extend the analysis along three lines: the Digital Omnibus package, provisionally agreed for its AI Act component in May 2026 but still in legislative process for its GDPR, Data Act, and NIS2 components, will require revision of several chapters once adopted; the implementability gaps identified in Chapter 8 — particularly machine unlearning, cross-regulatory compliance reasoning, and continuous compliance monitoring — constitute a concrete research agenda; and building the integrated, cross-regulation machine-readable compliance profile that Chapter 7 shows does not yet exist remains one of the most consequential open problems this deliverable surfaces, and one the HARNES project is positioned to address in its later deliverables

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable is produced within Work Package 2 (WP2) of the HARNES project, *Harnessing AI and Data-Intensive Technologies*, whose overarching objective is to develop methods and tools for compliance with AI and data regulations. D2.6 sits at the foundation of that objective: before compliance tools can be designed, evaluated, or deployed, the regulatory framework they are meant to operationalise must be understood from a technical standpoint.

The purpose of this document is therefore to analyse the EU AI and data regulatory landscape through an **informatics lens**. This is a deliberate and defining choice. The legal content of the regulations in scope has been addressed, or will be addressed, by Work Package 1 (WP1), which approaches the same landscape from a jurisprudential perspective. D2.6 does not duplicate that work. Its question is different: not *what do these regulations say*, but *what do they require of technical systems, data architectures, and the engineers and data scientists who build them?*

The regulations in scope are organised into two primary clusters:

- **The Data Regulatory Cluster**, encompassing core data regulations (GDPR, Data Act, Data Governance Act, ePrivacy Directive, eIDAS 2.0, EECC, Open Data Directive, Interoperable Europe Act), and three sub-clusters: AI (AI Act, Product Liability Directive), Platforms (DSA, DMA), and Health (EHDS, MDR/IVDR).
- **The Cybersecurity Regulatory Cluster**, encompassing NIS2, the Cyber Resilience Act, DORA, EUCC, the Telecommunications Security Act, and related instruments.

Figure 1.1. Growth of the EU digital regulatory framework in scope of D2.6, 2002–2025. Each node represents a legislative instrument by year of adoption, coloured by cluster. The diagram illustrates the long stability of the framework anchored by the 2002 ePrivacy Directive, the structural shift introduced by the GDPR in 2016, and the sharp acceleration from 2022 onwards — when seven instruments were adopted in a single year — reflecting the EU's systematic expansion from data protection into AI governance, platform accountability, cybersecurity resilience, and sectoral data access.

This document does not constitute a legal commentary on any of the instruments listed above. It is an analysis of the technical obligations, architectural constraints, role definitions, and implementation requirements that these instruments generate for systems built with, or subject to, AI and data-intensive technologies.

1.2 Importance of AI and Data Regulation for Technical Systems

The past decade has witnessed a fundamental transformation in the relationship between legal regulation and technical systems. For much of the history of software engineering, regulation was an external constraint, something that legal and compliance departments managed after a system had been designed. The emerging EU regulatory framework for AI and data has made that model untenable.

The AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689) imposes requirements on AI systems that are inseparable from how those systems are designed and deployed: the requirement for human oversight is not a policy choice that can be bolted on; it demands specific architectural provisions for intervention, monitoring, and logging. The requirement for transparency in high-risk systems is not a documentation exercise; it demands that model behaviour be explainable at the level of individual outputs. The prohibition on certain AI practices is not a use-policy; it constrains what training objectives, data sources, and deployment configurations are permissible. Regulation, in other words, has entered the design space.

The same is true across the data regulatory cluster. The GDPR's principle of data protection by design and by default (Article 25) is an explicit mandate to embed privacy into system architecture from the outset. The Data Act's requirements for interoperability and data portability constrain the data models and APIs that systems must expose. The Data Governance Act creates new categories of technical actors, such as data intermediaries, and data altruism organisations, whose operational requirements must be technically instantiated. The EHDS defines access regimes, consent mechanisms, and secondary use conditions for health data that must be reflected in the systems that process it.

The consequence is straightforward: engineers, data architects, and AI developers working in the EU regulatory space can no longer treat regulation as someone else's problem. They are, in many instances, the primary addressees of regulatory obligations, either directly (as providers or

deployers under the AI Act) or indirectly (as the people who make the technical choices that determine whether a system is compliant or not). This deliverable is, among other things, a mapping of that reality.

Beyond the immediate obligations of individual regulations, the regulatory framework has systemic significance for technical practice. It is reshaping what counts as good engineering: documentation, auditability, explainability, and resilience are no longer quality preferences but legal requirements. It is reshaping procurement: public and private sector entities are increasingly required to verify compliance before deploying AI systems. And it is reshaping the research agenda: the gap between what regulations require and what current tools can deliver is one of the most productive open problems in the field (see D2.2 for a survey of the current state of compliance tools and methods).

1.3 Challenges in Technically Interpreting AI and Data Regulations

Translating regulatory text into technical requirements is not a straightforward exercise, and the challenges are worth naming at the outset, both to set expectations for the analysis that follows and to contextualise the limitations that the reader will encounter throughout this document.

Terminological indeterminacy. EU regulations are written in legal language, which is simultaneously precise in its normative intent and imprecise in its technical referents. The AI Act defines an "AI system" as "a machine-based system that, for a given set of objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, recommendations, decisions, or content", a definition that is deliberately broad to ensure future-proofing, but which creates genuine uncertainty about which systems fall within scope. Terms such as "meaningful human oversight", "substantial modification", or "appropriate technical and organisational measures" carry legal weight without specifying the technical forms they may take.

Multi-layered normativity. The regulatory framework is not flat. Primary legislation sits alongside harmonised standards (from ENISA, CEN, CENELEC, and ISO), sector-specific guidance, soft law instruments such as codes of practice and guidelines from the European AI Office, and Member State transposition. A technical system may need to satisfy requirements originating from several layers simultaneously, and the interactions between them are not always consistent. This document maps the primary legislative layer in detail; the standards and soft law layer is addressed in Chapter 3.

Regulatory interactions and tensions. The regulations in scope were not designed as a unified system. They were produced by different Directorates-General of the European Commission, over different timescales, in response to different perceived problems. The result is a framework with significant overlaps, some tensions, and occasional contradictions. A data minimisation obligation under GDPR may sit uneasily alongside a data retention obligation under NIS2; a transparency requirement under the DSA may interact in complex ways with a trade secret protection under the Data Act. These interactions are addressed in Chapter 6.

The implementability gap. Some regulatory requirements are, at present, technically difficult or impossible to implement fully. The requirement for explainability in high-risk AI systems is the best-known example: current explainability methods offer approximations of model behaviour, not authoritative accounts of it. The requirement for purpose limitation in data spaces raises open questions about how technical enforcement mechanisms can guarantee the restriction. This deliverable notes these gaps where they arise; they constitute, in part, the research agenda that WP2 of HARNES is designed to address.

Jurisdictional scope. The analysis in this document focuses primarily on EU-level instruments. It does not provide a systematic account of Member State transpositions, which introduce significant variation in how directives are implemented in national law. Where transposition variation is particularly consequential for technical implementation, as in the case of NIS2, it is duly noted.

2 METHODOLOGY

D2.6 is an analytical deliverable. Its goal is not to survey a field of practice — that is the function of D2.2 — but to interpret a body of law from a technical standpoint: to determine what EU regulations on AI and data require of systems, architectures, and engineers, and to identify where those requirements are technically tractable, where they are contested, and where they remain open research problems. The methodology must therefore be appropriate to that interpretive task.

This chapter describes the two methodological commitments that structure the analysis: a doctrinal approach to reading regulatory instruments, adapted for technical rather than purely legal interpretation; and a purposive, structured approach to collecting the primary and secondary sources that inform that reading.

2.1 Literature Review Approach

The analytical method adopted in D2.6 is *doctrinal regulatory analysis with technical operationalisation*, as outlined by Bhat (2020) and earlier by Breaux et al (2006). This is the same primary method used in D1.1, which applies doctrinal legal methodology supplemented by socio-legal and interdisciplinary analysis to map the EU AI and data regulatory framework from a legal perspective. D2.6 shares the doctrinal starting point but diverges in its question: where D1.1 asks what the law says and how it allocates roles, rights, obligations, and deterrence mechanisms, D2.6 asks what the same law requires of technical systems, data architectures, and the engineers who build them. The two deliverables are therefore complementary rather than sequential — they were developed in parallel, address the same regulatory corpus from different disciplinary angles, and are designed to be read together.

The doctrinal method, as applied here, proceeds in three stages.

Stage 1: Identification of normative content. Each instrument in scope is read for its normative provisions — those that impose obligations, prohibitions, permissions, or rights in the sense established in Section 3.1. This stage draws on the tools of statutory interpretation recognised in EU law: literal reading of the operative text; contextual reading against the recitals, other provisions of the same instrument, and related instruments; and teleological reading against the stated objectives of the regulation. Recitals are treated as interpretively significant but not independently normative. Where the text is genuinely ambiguous, the interpretive position of the relevant supervisory authority — the EDPB for GDPR, the European AI Office for the AI Act, ENISA for NIS2 and the CRA — is treated as the default unless there are strong technical reasons to depart from it.

Stage 2: Technical operationalisation. Each normative provision identified in Stage 1 is analysed for its technical implications: what must a system do, or refrain from doing, or be capable of demonstrating, in order to comply? This stage is the primary analytical contribution of D2.6. It involves mapping legal language to engineering concepts — design requirements, architectural

constraints, data structures, process steps, logging obligations, documentation artefacts — and identifying where that mapping is determinate, where it requires further interpretive work, and where it is genuinely indeterminate pending guidance, harmonised standards, or supervisory practice. The analytical vocabulary for this mapping is established in Chapter 3.

Stage 3: Gap and tension identification. Where the technical operationalisation of a provision conflicts with the operationalisation of another provision from the same or a different instrument, or where no current technical method can fully satisfy a requirement, the gap or tension is identified and analysed. These gaps constitute, in part, the research agenda that WP2 of HARNES is designed to address, and they are treated in depth in Chapters 8 and 10.

Figure 2.1. The three-stage analytical method adopted in D2.6. Stage 1 extracts normative provisions from each in-scope instrument using the tools of EU statutory interpretation. Stage 2 maps each provision to its technical implications — design requirements, architectural constraints, and documentation obligations — identifying where that mapping is determinate, requires further interpretive work, or is genuinely indeterminate. Stage 3 identifies gaps and tensions, both within and across instruments, where operationalisation conflicts or where no current technical method can fully satisfy a requirement. The outputs of each stage feed directly into the substantive chapters of the deliverable.

Secondary literature. The doctrinal analysis is informed by three categories of secondary source, consulted where they resolve genuine interpretive uncertainty or provide evidence about the technical feasibility of compliance.

Academic literature was identified through searches across major databases and repositories including Scopus, Web of Science, the ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, SSRN, and arXiv, complemented by forward and backward snowballing. Given D2.6's engineering orientation, search terms combined instrument names with technical operationalisation concepts — for example, "AI Act" with "conformity assessment" or "risk management system"; "GDPR" with "privacy by design" or "data minimisation"; "NIS2" with "incident reporting" or "security measures" — rather than with doctrinal legal concepts. The search horizon runs from January 2016 to June 2026, with particular weight given to material published after 2022 for the more recently enacted instruments.

Guidance and opinions of supervisory authorities: the EDPB, national data protection authorities, the European AI Office, ENISA, and the EMA for health-device-adjacent material. These are treated as interpretively authoritative within their domain — not legally binding in the formal sense, but the closest available statement of how primary law will be applied in practice, and therefore the most operationally relevant secondary source for engineers designing compliance into systems.

Technical standards and specifications: published and draft standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1 and its subcommittees (notably SC 27 for information security and SC 42 for AI), CEN/CENELEC JTC 21, ETSI, and ENISA's technical guidelines. Standards are analysed both for substantive content and for formal status — whether formally harmonised, in draft, or voluntary — since that status determines whether they create a presumption of conformity and therefore a stable engineering target. The standards layer is the subject of Chapter 5.

What the literature review is not. D2.6 does not apply the multivocal literature review (MLR) protocol used in D2.2. The MLR, with its structured keyword search across multiple databases, systematic inclusion and exclusion criteria, and quantitative synthesis of retrieved papers, is designed to characterise a body of existing research and practice. That is the appropriate method for D2.2, whose object of analysis is a field of compliance tools where grey literature from market actors is first-class evidence. D2.6's object of analysis is regulatory text, which is authoritative independently of how much academic attention it has received. Importing the MLR apparatus would create a methodological mismatch; it would substitute the characterisation of a research field for the interpretation of legal instruments. The present chapter therefore describes the sources consulted and how they are used, without claiming the structured synthesis procedures of a formal systematic review.

2.2 Data Collection Method

The data-collection process for D2.6 is purposive: the goal is to assemble the sources needed to support the three analytical stages described in Section 2.1, not to achieve exhaustive coverage of any field of literature.

Regulatory corpus. The starting point is the assembly of the primary regulatory corpus, consisting of the full text of each instrument listed in Section 1.1 — regulations and directives, with their recitals, annexes, and implementing acts — retrieved from the Official Journal of the European Union via EUR-Lex. Each instrument is recorded with its Official Journal citation, current legal status (in force, partially applied, or under amendment), and the specific articles and annexes identified as technically significant through the Stage 1 reading. The Digital Omnibus amendments — provisionally agreed for the AI Act component on 7 May 2026 and still in legislative process for the GDPR, Data Act, and NIS2 components at the time of writing — are tracked separately and incorporated with explicit flags distinguishing settled from proposed law.

Provision extraction. Within each instrument, technically significant provisions are identified by a two-pass manual reading. The first pass identifies all provisions containing technical referents: specific references to data structures, system architectures, quantitative thresholds (the DORA four-hour notification window; the GDPR 72-hour breach notification clock; the AI Act's 10^{23} FLOP threshold for GPAI systemic-risk classification), or terms of art whose technical meaning requires interpretation. The second pass cross-references those provisions with supervisory authority guidance and academic literature to identify where interpretive consensus exists and where genuine uncertainty remains.

The output of provision extraction is a structured set of obligations, prohibitions, permissions, and rights that feeds directly into the technical analysis in Chapters 6 and 7, and into the mapping tables in Table 5.1 (regulatory requirements to technical constraints) and Table 7.1 (roles for technical persons).

Standards tracking. Where a regulatory provision delegates technical specification to a harmonised standard, or where a de facto standard has emerged as the operational benchmark in the absence of formal harmonisation, the relevant standard or specification is retrieved and incorporated. For standards still under development — as is the case for several CEN/CENELEC mandates under the AI Act and the CRA — available draft texts, mandate documentation, and public consultation records are used as proxies, with explicit caveats about their provisional status.

Cross-instrument interaction mapping. A distinct data-collection step constructs a matrix of provisions across instruments, identifying pairs or groups that address the same technical object — incident notification, data retention, conformity assessment, transparency disclosure, access control — and flagging potential overlaps, conflicts, or gaps. This matrix is the empirical input to the regulatory interaction analysis in Chapter 6, and is a point of direct connection with D1.1's Appendices which map the same instruments from a legal perspective.

Temporal scope. The regulatory corpus is treated as authoritative as of the date of this deliverable's completion. For the fastest-moving components of the landscape — the Digital Omnibus legislative process, the CEN/CENELEC harmonised standards programme under the AI Act and CRA, the GPAI Code of Practice, and the European AI Office's implementing guidelines — the analysis reflects the

status as of June 2026. Readers consulting this document after that date should verify the current status of instruments flagged as provisional or in development.

3 THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Before the regulatory clusters can be analysed instrument by instrument, the analytical apparatus used throughout this document needs to be made explicit. Three conceptual moves recur across every chapter that follows: legal norms are classified by their deontic modality so that each can be matched to the kind of technical mechanism it demands; the passage from legal text to a machine-processable representation is decomposed into discrete interpretive stages, each with its own sources of error; and the role of standards, soft law, and the data space as an architectural context is established as the connective tissue between abstract legal obligation and concrete system design. This chapter sets out each of these in turn, not as an exhaustive theory of legal informatics, but as the minimum conceptual vocabulary needed to read the technical analysis in the chapters that follow without ambiguity about what is being claimed.

3.1 Key Concepts: Obligations, Rights, and Prohibitions as Technical Requirements

The primary analytical operation performed throughout this document is the translation of legal norms into technical requirements. This section establishes the conceptual vocabulary for that operation.

Legal norms, in the tradition of deontic logic originating with von Wright (1951), can be classified according to their modality: an **obligation** (O) mandates that a certain state of affairs hold or that a certain action be performed; a **prohibition** (F) forbids an action or state; a **permission** (P) authorises an action that would otherwise be impermissible; and a **right** confers on its holder the ability to demand performance of a corresponding obligation. This taxonomy, developed further in D2.2 (Section 3.2), is not merely of theoretical interest: it determines what kind of technical mechanism a regulation requires.

An obligation generates a **design requirement**: something must be built in. The obligation under Article 9 of the AI Act for providers of high-risk AI systems to establish a risk management system is a design requirement: a system without a risk management infrastructure is non-compliant by construction, regardless of how it behaves at runtime.

A prohibition generates a **constraint**: something must be prevented. The prohibition under Article 5 of the AI Act on AI systems that deploy subliminal techniques to manipulate behaviour is a constraint on training objectives and deployment configurations. It cannot be verified purely at the level of outputs; it requires inspection of the system's design intent.

A permission defines a **boundary condition**: certain actions are permissible within stated parameters. The GDPR's permissions for processing under Article 6 establish the conditions under which data flows are lawful; in technical terms, they define the access control conditions that a system must enforce.

A right generates a **service requirement** (see, for example, Breaux 2009): the system must be capable of responding to the right's exercise. The GDPR's right of access (Article 15), right to rectification (Article 16), and right to erasure (Article 17) all require that systems be capable of locating, correcting, and deleting data at the level of individual data subjects, requirements that have direct implications for database architecture, data lineage tracking, and audit logging.

This four-part taxonomy structures the technical analysis in Chapters 4 and 5. For each regulation, obligations, prohibitions, permissions, and rights are identified and their technical implications derived. The analysis does not aim to be exhaustive, which would require a commentary of a different kind, but to identify the technically consequential provisions and map them to the categories of engineering and architectural response they demand.

3.2 From Legal Text to Machine-Readable Norms

The formalisation of legal text into representations that can be processed by computational systems is a long-standing research problem, with contributions ranging from the early logic programming encoding of the British Nationality Act (Sergot et al., 1986) to contemporary approaches using ontologies, knowledge graphs, and large language models (see D2.2 for a survey). This document does not itself produce formal encodings; it provides the interpretive groundwork that formal encodings require.

The process of moving from legal text to machine-readable norms passes through several stages of interpretation, each of which introduces the possibility of error and requires methodological care:

Syntactic parsing identifies the normative sentences in a legal text, those that express obligations, prohibitions, permissions, or rights, and distinguishes them from definitional provisions, recitals, and preambles. Legal language does not always signal normativity transparently: "shall", "must", and "is required to" are clearly deontic, but "should", "may", and "is encouraged to" occupy a more ambiguous normative space that varies across instruments and jurisdictions.

Semantic disambiguation determines the referents of the normative sentence, who is the norm-subject (the entity bearing the obligation or right), what is the norm-act (the action or state the norm concerns), and what are the norm-conditions (the circumstances under which the norm applies). In the AI Act, for instance, the distinction between "provider" and "deployer" as norm-subjects is technically consequential: a provider obligation cannot be discharged by a deployer, and vice versa, even where the technical action at issue is the same.

Operationalisation maps the disambiguated norm to a concrete technical requirement: a data structure, a process step, an access control rule, a logging obligation. This is the stage at which legal indeterminacy becomes most visible. "Appropriate technical and organisational measures" (a formulation that appears across GDPR, NIS2, and the AI Act) cannot be operationalised without reference to the specific system, threat model, and deployment context. This document provides operationalisation guidance at the level of architectural pattern and design principle; system-specific operationalisation is necessarily context-dependent.

Verification determines whether a deployed system satisfies the operationalised requirement. The compliance checking methods and tools surveyed in D2.2 address this stage. D2.6 is upstream of D2.2: its output is the set of requirements that compliance checking tools are designed to verify.

The relationship between D2.6 and D2.2 is therefore constitutive: this document provides the normative input that compliance tools take as their target. Chapter 8 returns to this relationship explicitly, mapping the regulatory requirements analysed here to the categories of compliance tool identified in D2.2.

3.3 Regulatory Frameworks and Standards

3.3.1 Harmonised Standards and Technical Specifications

EU regulations increasingly delegate the specification of technical requirements to harmonised standards produced by European standardisation bodies (CEN, CENELEC, ETSI) and, for cybersecurity, ENISA. A harmonised standard, once referenced in the Official Journal, creates a presumption of conformity: a system that complies with the standard is presumed to comply with the corresponding regulatory requirement. This has significant practical implications.

For the AI Act, the European Commission has mandated CEN/CENELEC to develop harmonised standards across a range of requirements including risk management (ISO/IEC 23894), data quality (ISO/IEC 5259 series), transparency (ISO/IEC 12792), and robustness. At the time of writing, many of these standards are still under development. In the interim, the AI Act's requirements must be operationalised without the presumption of conformity that harmonised standards would provide, which increases uncertainty for system developers.

For cybersecurity, ENISA has produced technical guidelines under NIS2, and the Cyber Resilience Act establishes a certification framework that references existing schemes such as the EUCC (EU Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for ICT Products). The relationship between EUCC certification and AI Act compliance is one of the framework's underspecified interactions: an AI system that is also a product with digital elements may need to satisfy both schemes, and the scoping criteria do not always align.

For data regulations, ISO/IEC 27001 (information security management) and ISO/IEC 27701 (privacy information management, extending 27001 for GDPR) are widely referenced as technical benchmarks, though neither is formally harmonised under GDPR. The Data Act and Data Governance Act are newer, and their associated standardisation landscape is less developed.

3.3.2 Soft Law: Guidelines, Codes of Practice, and Certifications

Below primary legislation and harmonised standards, a substantial layer of soft law shapes how regulations are technically interpreted and implemented. This layer includes:

Guidelines from supervisory authorities. The European Data Protection Board (EDPB) has produced guidelines on topics ranging from data portability to the use of biometric data that are technically consequential even though they do not have binding legal force. The European AI Office, established under the AI Act, is producing analogous guidance for AI systems. National data protection authorities (DPAs) have produced guidance that varies across Member States, introducing jurisdictional variation in technical expectations.

Codes of practice. The AI Act explicitly provides for codes of practice as a mechanism for providers of general-purpose AI models to demonstrate compliance in advance of harmonised standards. The first Code of Practice for General-Purpose AI was finalised in 2025 and contains technical commitments on transparency, safety testing, and incident reporting that constitute de facto technical requirements for GPAI model providers.

Certifications and audit schemes. GDPR Article 42 provides for certification mechanisms; several Member States have developed certification schemes, and the European Data Protection Seal is under development. AI Act Article 49 provides for EU certification of high-risk AI systems by notified bodies. These schemes translate regulatory requirements into auditable technical criteria.

The soft law layer is not systematically analysed in this document (this would require a deliverable of its own) but it is referenced where it provides the most operational technical guidance available for a given requirement.

3.4 Data Spaces as a Regulatory Context

A significant portion of the regulatory framework analysed in this document applies in, or is shaped by, the context of data spaces, federated data sharing infrastructures in which multiple actors exchange data under shared governance rules. Data spaces are the primary architectural paradigm for implementing the EU Data Strategy, and several of the instruments in the Data Regulatory Cluster (the Data Act, the Data Governance Act, the EHDS in particular) were designed with data spaces explicitly in mind.

The concept of a data space introduces a layer of technical complexity that regulatory analysis conducted at the level of individual systems may miss. In a data space:

- Data does not reside in a single system but is distributed across multiple participants, each of whom may be subject to different national implementations of the same directive.
- Data flows are mediated by technical protocols (such as the IDSA Dataspace Protocol or the GAIA-X Trust Framework) that must themselves encode regulatory requirements, for instance, usage control policies that enforce purpose limitation at the point of data sharing.
- Roles such as data provider, data consumer, data intermediary, and data space operator do not map cleanly onto the regulatory categories of data controller, data processor, and data subject, creating interpretive uncertainty about which regulatory obligations apply to which actor.

The analysis of the Data Regulatory Cluster in Chapter 4 therefore distinguishes, where relevant, between requirements as they apply to individual systems and requirements as they apply in the context of data spaces. This is particularly important for the EHDS, the Data Act, and the Data Governance Act, all of which presuppose data space-like architectures in their operational provisions.

4 THE REGULATORY LANDSCAPE: CLUSTERS AND INSTRUMENTS

With the analytical vocabulary of Chapter 3 in place, this chapter turns to the regulatory landscape itself: which instruments fall within scope, how they are grouped for the purposes of this analysis, and why. It first sets out the clustering structure used throughout the remainder of the document and the rationale behind it, then situates this deliverable relative to D1.1 and the wider work of WP1, and finally states explicitly what has been left out of scope and why. The result is not a legal taxonomy but a working map, oriented toward the compliance problem as it confronts an engineer rather than as it might be organised in a treatise.

4.1 Overview and Rationale for Clustering

The EU regulatory framework for AI and data-intensive systems consists of more than a dozen instruments enacted over a decade, by different Directorates-General, in response to different perceived policy problems. Presenting them as an undifferentiated list would obscure the structural relationships between them; organising them into an arbitrary taxonomy would impose artificial coherence on a landscape that is genuinely disorderly. This chapter adopts a clustering approach that is neither purely thematic nor purely chronological but reflects the technical dependencies that actually structure an engineer's compliance problem: which instruments apply to the same system, the same data flow, or the same actor simultaneously.

Two primary clusters are used throughout this document:

The **Data Regulatory Cluster** encompasses the instruments whose primary object is the governance of data — its collection, processing, sharing, access, retention, and portability. Within this cluster, four sub-clusters are distinguished: core data regulations (GDPR, Data Act, Data Governance Act, ePrivacy Directive, eIDAS 2.0, EEC, Open Data Directive, Interoperable Europe Act), an AI sub-cluster (AI Act, revised Product Liability Directive), a platform sub-cluster (DSA, DMA), and a health sub-cluster (EHDS, MDR/IVDR). The sub-cluster structure is motivated by technical specificity: the AI Act imposes requirements on a category of technical system that interacts with data in distinctive ways, and the health and platform sub-clusters address domains where specialist technical obligations are layered on top of the general data framework.

The **Cybersecurity Regulatory Cluster** encompasses the instruments whose primary object is the security and resilience of digital systems and critical infrastructure: NIS2, the Cyber Resilience Act, DORA, the EUCC certification scheme, the Regulation on Cybersecurity Measures for EU Institutions, and the Telecommunications Security Act. These instruments are technically distinct from the data cluster in that they are primarily concerned with threat models, vulnerability management, and incident response rather than data governance, though — as Chapter 8 documents — they interact with the data cluster at multiple points.

The clustering structure is a tool for exposition, not a claim about legal taxonomy. An AI system processing health data in a cloud environment operated by a financial institution may simultaneously be subject to the AI Act, GDPR, EHDS, DORA, NIS2, and the CRA — all five clusters touched at once. The chapters that follow analyse each cluster in turn; the interactions are the subject of Chapter 8.

Within each cluster, the analysis follows a consistent structure: each instrument is examined for the technical obligations it generates (in the sense of Section 3.1), the architectural constraints it imposes, the roles it creates or modifies, and the standards or soft-law instruments that provide operational guidance for its implementation. The analysis does not aim to be a legal commentary — it does not engage with interpretive debates about legislative history or doctrinal consistency except where those debates have technically consequential implications — but to map the compliance landscape as it presents to a technically informed reader.

4.2 Instruments Out of Scope and Justification

The EU digital regulatory acquis is broad, and D2.6 cannot address every instrument that touches AI or data-intensive systems. Several categories of instrument are deliberately excluded, and the exclusions are worth justifying explicitly.

Member State transpositions. The analysis focuses on EU-level instruments. Directives — NIS2, the ePrivacy Directive, the Data Act's implementing provisions in some Member States — require

national transposition, and transpositions introduce significant variation. D2.6 notes where transposition variation is technically consequential (particularly for NIS2, where Member States have exercised their discretion in ways that affect the technical obligations of essential and important entities) but does not provide a systematic survey of national law. Such a survey would require a separate deliverable for each Member State and is outside the scope of WP2.

Sector-specific financial regulation beyond DORA. The Markets in Financial Instruments Directive (MiFID II), the Capital Requirements Regulation (CRR), and the Solvency II Directive each impose data and algorithmic system requirements on financial sector entities that go beyond the general EU digital framework. These instruments are excluded because their technical requirements are substantially addressed by sector-specific compliance functions within financial institutions and because the overlap with the HARNES project's primary focus on AI and data systems in the broader economy is limited. DORA is included because its scope and its interactions with NIS2 and GDPR make it technically consequential for any organisation in the financial sector deploying AI systems.

The EU Artificial Intelligence Liability Directive (now discontinued). The draft AI Liability Directive, published by the Commission in September 2022 as a companion to the AI Act, was effectively withdrawn from the legislative process in February 2025 without having been adopted (European Parliament, 2025). It is not analysed in this document. Where liability questions are relevant to the analysis — notably in connection with the revised Product Liability Directive and its interaction with the AI Act — they are addressed under those instruments.

Trade law and third-country equivalency decisions. The EU-US Data Privacy Framework (Commission Decision 2023/1795, replacing the invalidated Privacy Shield), adequacy decisions under GDPR Article 45, and the EU's digital trade chapters in association agreements create significant data-flow obligations but are predominantly legal rather than technical in their implementation demands. They are excluded from the detailed analysis, though the architecture of international data transfers is noted where it affects the technical design of data processing systems.

Standards bodies' internal working documents. Draft standards, working group minutes, and national-body comments within ISO/IEC JTC 1, CEN/CENELEC JTC 21, and ETSI are tracked as part of the literature review methodology but are not cited as normative sources. Only published standards and formally published drafts for public comment are treated as having interpretive weight.

The proposed EU AI Liability Directive's replacement instruments. Following the withdrawal of the AI Liability Directive, the Commission has indicated that redress for AI-caused harm will be addressed through enhanced application of the revised Product Liability Directive combined with national civil liability frameworks. At the time of writing, no replacement legislative proposal has been published. This area is therefore treated as legally unsettled and is flagged in the relevant sections as a gap in the current framework.

The instruments retained in scope are those that, taken together, define the primary compliance architecture for an EU-based or EU-market-facing organisation developing, deploying, or processing

data with AI and data-intensive technologies. The scope is large enough to capture the constraint satisfaction problem that engineers actually face; it is bounded tightly enough to be analytically tractable within the resources of a single deliverable.

4.3 Relationship to D1.1 and WP1

D2.6 is produced within Work Package 2 of the HARNES project. Its relationship to the outputs of Work Package 1, and in particular to Deliverable D1.1, requires explicit statement because the two deliverables address overlapping material from different analytical angles.

D1.1 analyses the legal content of the EU regulatory framework from a jurisprudential perspective. Its scope encompasses the AI Act, the GDPR and associated data framework (ePrivacy Directive, DGA, Data Act, DSA, DMA, Law Enforcement Directive), the e-Commerce Directive, the New Legislative Framework, the revised Product Liability Directive, the Charter of Fundamental Rights, the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union as constitutional bases, the European Declaration on Digital Rights, the Principles for the Digital Decade, and the HLEG Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. D1.1's primary question is legal: what do these instruments say, what rights and obligations do they create, and how do they relate to one another as a matter of EU law?

D2.6's primary question is technical: what do these same instruments require of systems, data architectures, and engineers? The deliverables are complementary rather than competitive. D2.6 draws on D1.1 for its legal interpretation of ambiguous provisions and does not independently adjudicate interpretive legal disputes. Where D1.1 establishes that a provision has a particular legal meaning, D2.6 takes that meaning as given and proceeds to ask what technical implementation it demands. Where D1.1 has not yet addressed a provision that is technically consequential, D2.6 provides an engineering-oriented reading and flags the interpretive uncertainty.

Several instruments that fall within D1.1's scope are also within D2.6's scope; several that fall within D2.6's scope (notably the CRA, NIS2, DORA, and EUCC) are outside D1.1's scope, reflecting the different disciplinary focus of WP1 and WP2. This document does not treat the WP1/WP2 boundary as a division of labour that precludes cross-reference: where a legal interpretation developed in D1.1 affects the engineering analysis in D2.6, the cross-reference is made explicit.

The practical consequence for the reader is this: D2.6 is not a substitute for D1.1 for legal advice, and D1.1 is not a substitute for D2.6 for technical implementation guidance. The two documents are designed to be read together by the interdisciplinary teams — combining legal, regulatory, and engineering expertise — that the HARNES project exists to support.

5 STANDARDS AS TECHNICAL BRIDGES

Between primary legislation and its concrete technical implementation lies a critical intermediate layer: technical standards. EU regulations increasingly delegate the specification of how obligations are to be met to standards bodies, certification schemes, and soft-law instruments, and they do so through a legal mechanism — the presumption of conformity — that has direct engineering consequences. This chapter analyses that mechanism, surveys the current state of the standards landscape for each cluster in scope, and maps the gaps where harmonised standards do not yet exist and engineers must navigate compliance without their guidance.

5.1 The Presumption of Conformity and Its Engineering Implications

The legal device of the presumption of conformity connects the general language of primary legislation to the quantitative, testable, and auditable specifications that engineering practice requires. Under EU law, where a product or system complies with a harmonised standard whose reference has been published in the Official Journal of the European Union, it is presumed to meet the corresponding essential or mandatory requirements of the applicable legislation. This presumption is rebuttable — a supervisory authority or notified body may establish non-compliance even for a conforming system — but it shifts the burden of proof and provides the closest available equivalent to a safe harbour in EU technical regulation.

For engineers and system architects, the presumption of conformity has three practical implications.

First, it provides a stable, testable target. A harmonised standard translates the regulatory language — "appropriate technical and organisational measures", "state of the art", "risk-proportionate controls" — into specific technical criteria, test procedures, and documentation requirements. A system designed and documented against a harmonised standard can be audited by a third party against those criteria without requiring the auditor to make independent interpretive judgments about what the regulation requires.

Second, it establishes a documented baseline for liability purposes. Where a data breach, an AI system failure, or a cybersecurity incident results in regulatory investigation or litigation, compliance with a harmonised standard is evidence — not conclusive, but substantial — that the system met the applicable regulatory requirements at the time of deployment. In the absence of harmonised standards, this evidentiary baseline must be reconstructed case by case from the regulatory text, supervisory authority guidance, and the state of the art as it existed at the relevant time, a substantially less certain foundation.

Third, it constrains what counts as a "substantial modification" that would require a fresh conformity assessment. Where a system has been assessed against a harmonised standard, a modification that keeps the system within the standard's scope does not, in principle, invalidate the conformity assessment. A modification that takes the system outside the standard's scope, or that addresses a requirement for which the standard provides the primary benchmark, may require re-assessment.

The engineering implication is straightforward: where harmonised standards exist, building to them is almost always the rational compliance strategy. Where they do not yet exist — as is currently the case for several AI Act requirements — engineers must construct an equivalent justification from first principles, which is more costly, more uncertain, and more exposed to supervisory discretion.

5.2 Standards Under the AI Act

5.2.1 JTC 21 Work Programme and ISO/IEC 42001

The primary standardisation mandate for the AI Act has been issued to CEN/CENELEC Joint Technical Committee 21 on Artificial Intelligence. JTC 21 was established in 2021 (Leyden, 2025) with a mandate to develop European standards across a range of AI-relevant technical domains. The Commission's formal standardisation mandate under the AI Act (Mandate M/601) was issued in 2023 and covers risk management, data quality, transparency, robustness, accuracy, and cybersecurity for AI systems. At the time of writing, a number of JTC 21 standards are in draft or under development, and few have been formally harmonised by publication in the Official Journal.

In parallel, ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC 42 (Artificial Intelligence) has developed ISO/IEC 42001:2023, an AI management system standard modelled structurally on ISO/IEC 27001. ISO/IEC 42001 establishes requirements for an organisation-level AI management system, covering policies, risk management, human oversight mechanisms, and continual improvement. It is not a product standard — it does not certify specific AI systems — but it provides a framework against which organisational processes for AI development and deployment can be audited. Several Member State supervisory authorities have indicated that ISO/IEC 42001 certification may serve as partial evidence of compliance with AI Act Article 17 (quality management system) obligations, though formal harmonisation under the AI Act has not been achieved. A formal certification scheme against ISO/IEC 42001, developed by accreditation bodies in Germany, the Netherlands, and the UK, is operational and increasingly referenced in procurement specifications.

5.2.2 Data Quality, Transparency, Robustness: Current State

For the specific technical requirements of the AI Act, the standards landscape is uneven.

Data quality. ISO/IEC 5259 (Data quality for analytics and machine learning) is a multi-part series that addresses data quality dimensions relevant to AI Act Article 10(2) requirements for training, validation, and testing datasets. Parts 1 through 4 of the series have been published, covering data quality terminology, key characteristics, data quality process framework, and data quality process implementation guide respectively. These standards provide a vocabulary and a process framework for data quality management, but they do not prescribe quantitative thresholds — what level of missing data, what degree of class imbalance, what bias metrics — that would allow a system to be certified as compliant with Article 10's representativeness requirement without additional system-specific analysis.

Transparency and explainability. ISO/IEC 12792 (Artificial intelligence — Transparency taxonomy of AI systems) has been published and provides a conceptual taxonomy for transparency properties. It is a foundational vocabulary standard rather than a compliance standard: it establishes what terms mean (transparency to whom, at what level of abstraction, through what mechanism) but does not itself constitute a testable transparency requirement. For the explainability dimension of AI Act Articles 13 and 14, no harmonised standard is yet available. Post-hoc explanation methods — SHAP, LIME, counterfactual explanations — are widely used in practice (Salih, 2025) but are not formalised in a standard that would support a conformity claim.

Robustness and accuracy. ISO/IEC TR 24029-2 (Assessment of the robustness of neural networks) and ISO/IEC 24028 (Overview of trustworthiness in AI) provide technical guidance on robustness evaluation, but neither constitutes a harmonised standard under the AI Act. AI Act Article 15 requires that high-risk AI systems be designed to achieve appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity throughout their lifecycle and to behave consistently in the face of errors, faults, or adversarial inputs. These requirements lack a harmonised standard equivalent, meaning that demonstrating compliance with Article 15 currently requires a bespoke technical assessment against the regulatory text and any applicable supervisory authority guidance, supplemented by reference to the state of the art in robustness evaluation.

5.2.3 Gaps and Interim Compliance Strategies

The absence of harmonised standards for several key AI Act requirements creates a compliance problem for organisations that must begin building conformity assessments now, in advance of the August 2026 application date for high-risk AI system obligations. Two interim strategies are most commonly employed.

The first is the use of pre-normative technical specifications. CEN/CENELEC has the ability to publish CEN Workshop Agreements (CWAs) and Technical Specifications (TSs) that are not fully harmonised standards but represent the closest available consensus on technical requirements for a given topic. JTC 21 is producing a number of such specifications, and some supervisory authorities have indicated willingness to treat compliance with CWA/TS-level documents as evidence of diligence in the absence of full harmonisation.

The second is the documentation of state-of-the-art justification. The AI Act's cybersecurity requirements in Article 15 explicitly reference the "state of the art", and the risk management requirements in Article 9 are calibrated against "generally acknowledged state-of-the-art" measures. An organisation that cannot point to a harmonised standard can instead demonstrate compliance by documenting that its technical choices reflect current best practice as established by peer-reviewed literature, ENISA guidelines, and the practice of comparable organisations. This requires a more intensive documentation effort and is more exposed to supervisory challenge, but it is legally permissible and is the approach most technically capable organisations are currently adopting.

5.3 Standards Under the GDPR and Data Cluster

5.3.1 ISO/IEC 27001 and 27701

ISO/IEC 27001:2022 (Information security management systems) is the most widely implemented information security standard globally, with the number of active certifications exceeding 70,000 as of the 2023 ISO Survey. For GDPR purposes, ISO/IEC 27001:2022 is not a harmonised standard — it is not referenced in the Official Journal as creating a presumption of conformity under GDPR Article 32 — but it is the closest available operational benchmark for the "appropriate technical and organisational measures" requirement. Supervisory authorities across Member States, including the CNIL (France), the BSI (Germany), and the ICO (UK), have referenced ISO/IEC 27001 compliance as relevant, if not conclusive, evidence of Article 32 compliance.

ISO/IEC 27701:2025 (Privacy information management, extending ISO/IEC 27001:2022 for GDPR) extends the 27001 framework to address the privacy-specific requirements of the GDPR. It provides a Privacy Information Management System (PIMS) framework that maps its controls to GDPR obligations. ISO/IEC 27701:2025 certification has been adopted as a compliance signal by several large data controllers and processors, particularly in the cloud services sector. The European Data Protection Board has not formally endorsed 27701:2025 as a GDPR certification mechanism under Article 42, but its practical adoption has outpaced the formal certification framework.

For the Data Act and Data Governance Act, no equivalent mature standard exists. ISO/IEC 27001:2022 and 27701:2025 address personal data and information security respectively, but the Data Act's obligations concern non-personal data generated by IoT devices and the rights of product users, while the DGA creates technical requirements for data intermediaries and altruism organisations that are not addressed by any current ISO/IEC standard. This gap is one of the most operationally consequential in the standards landscape: organisations implementing Data Act compliance cannot point to a recognised standard as a benchmark and must construct technical specifications from the regulatory text and emerging guidance.

5.3.2 Interoperability and Data Space Technical Specifications

The IDSA Dataspace Protocol (DSP), published by the International Data Spaces Association, provides a technical specification for data space connectors — the components that implement controlled data sharing in accordance with the Data Act and DGA's data-sharing and data-intermediary requirements. The DSP specifies protocols for catalogue publication, contract negotiation, and data transfer in a manner that allows usage control policies to be attached to data assets and enforced at the point of transfer.

The Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) project provides a reference implementation of the DSP and has been adopted as the foundation for several major European data space initiatives, including those in the automotive (Catena-X), manufacturing (Manufacturing-X), and energy sectors. The

European Commission's Data Spaces Support Centre has endorsed the DSP as the technical interoperability baseline for EHDS, agriculture, and mobility data spaces.

From a standards perspective, the DSP is a de facto specification rather than a formal standard: it has not been adopted by ISO/IEC, CEN/CENELEC, or ETSI, and it does not create a presumption of conformity under any EU regulation. However, its operational adoption across European data space initiatives means that compliance with the DSP is increasingly a practical prerequisite for participation in EU-funded data-sharing initiatives and for demonstrating compliance with the Data Act's interoperability requirements under Article 33.

5.3.3 EHDS Technical Specifications

The European Health Data Space Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2025/327) is among the most technically specific of the data cluster instruments, in part because health data interoperability has been the subject of standardisation efforts for decades. The EHDS mandates the use of the HL7 FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) standard as the technical basis for both primary-use (MyHealth@EU) and secondary-use (HealthData@EU) data exchange.

The EHDS technical specifications, developed by the eHealth Network and the European Commission's eHealth Interoperability Lab, include: the EHDS FHIR Implementation Guide (specifying profiles for specific health data categories including patient summaries, laboratory reports, and medical imaging metadata); the EHDS Data Quality Framework (specifying data quality indicators for secondary-use datasets); and the EHDS Access Conditions Policy (specifying the technical metadata requirements for secondary-use data permit requests). These specifications are not yet formally harmonised under the EHDS Regulation — the implementing acts specifying technical requirements for MyHealth@EU and HealthData@EU access bodies are still in development at the time of writing — but they constitute the closest available benchmark for EHDS technical compliance and are the reference documents that health data space implementers are building against.

The MDR/IVDR interaction with EHDS creates an additional standards layer: AI-enabled medical devices that are also in vitro diagnostic devices must satisfy IEC 62304 (software lifecycle requirements), ISO 14971 (risk management for medical devices), and ISO 13485 (quality management for medical devices), as well as the EHDS data-exchange requirements. The software-as-a-medical-device guidance from the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG 2019-11) provides interpretive guidance on the demarcation between software subject to MDR/IVDR and software subject primarily to the AI Act, but the boundary remains contested for complex AI systems that provide both clinical decision support and health data management functions.

5.4 Standards Under the Cybersecurity Cluster

5.4.1 EUCC Certification Schemes

The EU Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for ICT products (EUCC), established under the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity Act (Regulation (EU) 2019/881, the "Cybersecurity Act") and detailed in Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2024/482, provides a common European framework for the security certification of ICT products. The EUCC covers products at assurance levels "substantial" and "high", corresponding broadly to Common Criteria Evaluation Assurance Levels EAL 4+/5+ and EAL 6+/7 respectively.

For AI systems that are also ICT products — embedded AI, AI-enabled consumer devices, AI components in critical infrastructure control systems — the EUCC provides a pathway to demonstrating cybersecurity compliance that is recognised across EU Member States. The relationship between EUCC certification and AI Act Article 15 compliance is addressed in Chapter 8 in the context of the double-conformity problem for AI systems that are also products with digital elements under the CRA; the core point is that EUCC certification at the high assurance level is likely to satisfy AI Act cybersecurity requirements, but the current assurance level distribution of AI products in the market skews strongly towards "basic" level, which falls below the EUCC threshold and is assessed by the developer without third-party involvement.

5.4.2 CRA Harmonised Standards

The Cyber Resilience Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/2847) establishes mandatory cybersecurity requirements for all products with digital elements placed on the EU market. Its essential requirements are set out in Annex I: Part I covers security requirements for the product (including the absence of known exploitable vulnerabilities, secure default configurations, minimisation of attack surfaces, and protection of stored, transmitted, and processed data), and Part II covers vulnerability management requirements (disclosure, patching, SBOM maintenance, coordinated vulnerability disclosure).

The Commission has issued a standardisation mandate to CEN/CENELEC (Mandate M/608) and to ETSI for the development of harmonised standards addressing the CRA's Annex I requirements. At the time of writing, CEN/CENELEC Work Item 00/SC42/WG10 and ETSI's Cyber working groups are developing relevant standards, but none has yet been published in a harmonised state. The interim standard of reference for CRA essential requirement compliance is the combination of IEC 62443 (industrial cybersecurity), ETSI EN 303 645 (consumer IoT security), and ISO/IEC 27001 (information security management), together with ENISA's Technical Guidelines on the CRA (ENISA, 2025). Germany's BSI Technical Guideline TR-03183-2 (August 2025) has emerged as the most specific national interpretation of CRA Annex I Part II SBOM requirements and is widely cited as a de facto benchmark in the absence of a harmonised standard.

5.4.3 NIS2 Technical Guidelines from ENISA

The NIS2 Directive (Directive (EU) 2022/2555) requires Member States to establish national authorities and CSIRT capacities, and it requires essential and important entities to implement

"appropriate and proportionate technical, operational and organisational measures" to manage cybersecurity risks and to notify incidents to competent authorities. The directive's primary technical specification mechanism is through ENISA guidance rather than formal harmonised standards, reflecting NIS2's character as a directive (requiring Member State transposition) rather than a regulation.

ENISA occupies a structurally distinct position from bodies such as the EDPS or civil-society organisations because it is the EU's dedicated cybersecurity agency, established by Regulation (EU) 2019/881 (the Cybersecurity Act) with an explicit mandate to support the implementation of NIS2 and to assist Member States and operators in meeting its requirements. Unlike the EDPS, whose remit is the protection of personal data in EU institutions, or an NGO, whose guidance carries no institutional authority, ENISA operates as a technical arm of the NIS2 governance architecture: it receives mandatory incident notifications from operators, maintains the single reporting platform for actively exploited vulnerabilities under the CRA, contributes to the development of European cybersecurity certification schemes, and coordinates the CSIRTs Network. Its guidance is therefore not merely expert commentary on the law but an output of the body the law itself tasks with making NIS2 operationally workable. ENISA has produced a substantial body of technical guidelines under NIS2 and its predecessor NIS1, including: guidelines on minimum security measures for operators of essential services in specific sectors (energy, water, health, digital infrastructure, transport); the ENISA Threat Landscape reports, which establish the risk context against which proportionate measures must be calibrated; and technical guidance on incident notification content and formats. ENISA's "Technical Guidance on the Security Measures Under the NIS2 Directive" (published 2024) provides the most comprehensive currently available operationalisation of NIS2 Article 21's security measures across the ten risk-management categories specified in Article 21(2). This guidance has no formal presumption-of-conformity status but is widely used by national supervisory authorities as the benchmark for enforcement and by organisations as the specification for compliance programmes.

5.5 Where Harmonised Standards Do Not Yet Exist

The gaps in the harmonised standards landscape are as consequential as the areas covered. For several technically significant regulatory requirements, engineers must navigate compliance without the guidance — and the legal certainty — that a harmonised standard provides. The most operationally important gaps at the time of writing are the following.

AI Act explainability requirements (Articles 13 and 14). The AI Act itself does not require harmonised standard to exist for explainability, nor does it mandate their use: AI Act Article 40 makes harmonised standards voluntary, granting providers who apply them a presumption of conformity with the requirements to which those standards relate, but leaving organisations free to demonstrate compliance through other means. A harmonised standard addressing transparency and explainability has, however, been formally requested and is under active development (European Commission, 2023). In May 2023, CEN and CENELEC formally accepted standardisation request M/593 from the European Commission, charging JTC 21 with developing harmonised

standards to support AI Act compliance across risk management, transparency, human oversight, cybersecurity, and quality assurance requirements. The work item most directly relevant to explainability is prEN 18229-1 (Trustworthiness Framework Part 1: Logging, Transparency, Human Oversight), which is currently in draft. As of mid-2025, only eight of approximately thirty-five work items had been published, with a substantial portion not expected to reach a final vote until mid-2026, exceeding the original April 2025 deadline from the standardisation request by more than a year; in October 2025, CEN and CENELEC adopted an exceptional package of measures to accelerate delivery (CEN/CENELEC, 2025), targeting availability of the foundational standards by Q4 2026. Until those standards are published and referenced in the Official Journal, no harmonised standard for explainability exists (Cimadori et al, 2025). The AI Act requires that the output of high-risk AI systems be interpretable by deployers and users, but the technical mechanism for achieving that interpretability — local post-hoc explanations, inherently interpretable architectures, counterfactual explanations, attention visualisation — is unspecified in both the legislation and the draft standards. This is not merely a gap in the standards landscape; it reflects a genuine scientific uncertainty about what "sufficient" explainability means and how it can be tested, a problem discussed in Chapter 8 as one of the primary implementability challenges of the framework.

AI Act human oversight requirements (Article 14). The requirement that high-risk AI systems be designed such that natural persons can effectively oversee their operation, understand their outputs, and intervene where necessary has no harmonised standard equivalent. Human-factor standards (ISO 9241 series) and human-machine interface standards from the aerospace and automotive domains provide relevant technical vocabulary, but do not address the AI-specific challenge of meaningful oversight of systems whose behaviour is generated by statistical inference over high-dimensional inputs.

Data Act interoperability requirements (Articles 33–35). The Data Act's requirements for smart contract interoperability and for data portability standards have not yet been operationalised in harmonised standards. The Commission has been mandated to develop implementing acts specifying the essential requirements for smart contracts and the minimum technical specifications for interoperability, but at the time of writing these implementing acts are pending.

GPAI model evaluation requirements (AI Act Articles 55 and 53). The requirement that providers of GPAI models with systemic risk conduct adversarial testing sufficient to demonstrate that systemic risks are identified and mitigated has no harmonised evaluation standard. Red-teaming methodologies developed by AI safety researchers and the approaches specified in the GPAI Code of Practice provide practical guidance, but the absence of a standardised evaluation framework means that supervisory authorities retain wide discretion in determining whether a given model's evaluation programme is adequate.

DGA data intermediary technical requirements (Chapter II). The Data Governance Act establishes a regime for data intermediaries (data-sharing services) and requires their registration with national competent authorities, but the technical specifications for what infrastructure a data intermediary

must provide — security measures, access control, audit logging, interoperability requirements — are not addressed in a harmonised standard (European Commission, 2025c).

5.6 Mapping of Standards to Regulatory Instruments

The table below provides a summary mapping of the principal harmonised and de facto standards to the regulatory instruments analysed in this document. The table is limited to standards that explicitly address the legal requirements of the instrument in question — either by referencing the regulation by name, by being developed under a Commission standardisation mandate issued in support of that regulation, or by being formally scoped to its subject matter. This excludes the substantial body of work by CEN/CENELEC, ISO, and IEC that addresses adjacent topics — information security management, privacy engineering, software quality, risk assessment — without explicitly targeting a regulatory instrument. ISO/IEC 27001, for example, has extensive application to GDPR Article 32 security obligations in practice, but the standard itself does not reference GDPR and its scope predates and extends well beyond it; it therefore appears here only where it has been explicitly scoped to a regulatory requirement, not as a general security management reference. The table distinguishes between harmonised standards (adopted by CEN, CENELEC, or ETSI under a Commission mandate and published in the Official Journal, conferring a presumption of conformity), de facto benchmarks (widely used in compliance programmes against a specific regulatory requirement but without presumption-of-conformity status), and standards currently in development under an issued mandate.

Table 5.1. Mapping of regulatory instruments to their associated technical standards, distinguishing formally harmonised standards (published in the Official Journal with presumption-of-conformity effect), de facto benchmarks (widely adopted in practice without formal harmonisation), and standards currently in development. The table shows that formal harmonisation remains the exception rather than the rule across the framework, with only MDR/IVDR and EUCC backed by fully harmonised standards at the time of writing; most instruments rely instead on de facto benchmarks that carry no statutory presumption of conformity, and several of the newest instruments — the AI Act and the CRA in particular — have standardisation work still underway.

Regulatory Instrument	Relevant Harmonised Standard	De Facto Benchmark	In Development
AI Act (high-risk systems)	—	ISO/IEC 42001, ISO/IEC 5259 series, ISO/IEC 12792	CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 suite (Mandate M/601)
AI Act (GPAI models)	—	GPAI Code of Practice (2025)	CEN/CENELEC, ETSI GPAI standards
GDPR (Article 32 security)	—	ISO/IEC 27001, ISO/IEC 27701	—

Regulatory Instrument	Relevant Harmonised Standard	De Facto Benchmark	In Development
GDPR (Article 42 certification)	—	—	EU data protection seal (pending)
Data Act (interoperability)	—	IDSA Dataspace Protocol, EDC	Commission implementing acts (pending)
Data Governance Act	—	EDC, ODRL policy language	—
EHDS	—	HL7 FHIR, EHDS FHIR IGs	EHDS implementing acts (pending)
MDR/IVDR	EN IEC 62304, EN ISO 14971:2019, EN ISO 13485:2016	MDCG guidance	—
NIS2 (Article 21 measures)	—	ENISA Technical Guidelines	—
CRA (Annex I requirements)	—	IEC 62443, ETSI EN 303 645, BSI TR-03183-2	CEN/CENELEC Mandate M/608, ETSI
EUCC	EN ISO/IEC 15408:2023 series	—	—
DORA (ICT security)	—	ISO/IEC 27001 plus TIBER-EU	—

The structural message of this table is clear: for the newest and most technically ambitious instruments — the AI Act and the CRA in particular — the harmonised standards infrastructure has not yet caught up with the legislative obligation, and engineers are building compliance programmes against a moving target. The presumption of conformity, the cornerstone of the EU's New Legislative Framework approach to technical regulation, is not yet available for most AI Act requirements. The practical consequence is that first-mover organisations are constructing proprietary compliance architectures that will need to be revised when harmonised standards eventually arrive — creating a risk of lock-in and re-engineering costs that the Commission's Digital Omnibus simplification effort is, at least in part, designed to mitigate.

6 REGULATORY INTERACTIONS AND TENSIONS

The EU regulatory landscape relevant to AI and data-intensive systems was not designed as a unified corpus. Its constituent instruments — the GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679), the AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689), the Data Act (Regulation (EU) 2023/2854), the Data Governance Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/868), the Digital Services Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/2065), the NIS2 Directive (Directive (EU) 2022/2555), the Cyber Resilience Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/2847), the Digital Operational Resilience Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/2554), the European Health Data Space Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2025/327), and adjacent sectoral instruments — were drafted at different times, by different Directorates-General, and against different policy backdrops. Their cumulative application produces overlaps, latent conflicts, and implementation tensions that engineers, data architects, and AI developers must reconcile in concrete system designs. This chapter analyses those tensions from a technical standpoint and situates them against the European Commission's ongoing Digital Omnibus simplification effort initiated in November 2025.

The central thesis of this chapter is that the framework, viewed from an informatics standpoint, constitutes a constraint satisfaction problem: engineers must reconcile concurrent obligations from heterogeneous instruments within a single architecture, and several of these constraints are not simultaneously satisfiable with current technology. Identifying precisely where and why is the first step toward addressing it.

Figure 6.1. Cross-instrument regulatory tensions among the seven principal AI and data instruments in scope. Each edge denotes a documented point of friction between two instruments' technical requirements, labelled with the conflicting provisions and the nature of the tension (e.g., GDPR's data minimisation principle under Article 5 versus the AI Act's data sufficiency requirement under Article 10). The network illustrates that these tensions are not isolated anomalies but a structural property of the regulatory landscape, with GDPR positioned at the centre of the highest concentration of cross-instrument friction.

6.1 Overlaps and Conflicts Within and Across Clusters

6.1.1 GDPR versus NIS2: Data Minimisation Against Forensic Retention

The most operationally visible tension arises between GDPR Article 5(1)(c) — which requires that personal data be "adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed" (European Parliament and Council, 2016) — and the incident-detection, logging, and forensic obligations imposed by NIS2 Articles 21 and 23 (European Parliament and Council, 2022a). NIS2 transposing measures and supporting industry guidance commonly converge on a minimum log-retention horizon of eighteen months for security telemetry, with integrity guarantees that prevent tampering. Personal data is unavoidably present in those logs — IP addresses, user identifiers, mail flow records, authentication events — and any attempt to purge it within a shorter GDPR-compatible retention window risks destroying forensic evidence necessary for incident investigation.

From a technical perspective, the reconciliation strategy is architectural separation: pseudonymise or hash personal identifiers in the security log stream, isolate raw personal data in storage subject to GDPR retention schedules, and constrain analyst access via role-based controls. This approach is sound in principle but comes at non-trivial cost. Hunt & Hackett (2024) report that meeting these telemetry-retention obligations "can increase data ingestion costs by a factor of 3–10×" relative to baseline managed-detection-and-response services. The pseudonymisation approach also requires that the hashing or tokenisation scheme be keyed such that re-identification is reversible only under controlled conditions — effectively adding a key-management layer to the security operations infrastructure.

The tension is not resolved by the text of either regulation. GDPR Recital 49 acknowledges that processing personal data for network and information security purposes may constitute a legitimate interest, and the EDPB has endorsed a legitimate-interest basis for limited security-log retention, but the precise retention horizon, pseudonymisation standard, and access control architecture are left to organisational determination. The Digital Omnibus proposal, discussed below in Section 6.1.5, seeks to provide a single reporting framework that would partially rationalise these conflicting schedules, but does not eliminate the underlying architectural tension.

6.1.2 GDPR versus AI Act: Data Sufficiency Against Data Minimisation

A structurally similar but technically distinct tension arises from the interaction of GDPR Article 5(1)(b)'s purpose-limitation and Article 5(1)(c)'s data-minimisation principles with the AI Act's data quality and representativeness requirements under Article 10. AI Act Article 10(2) requires that training, validation, and testing datasets be "relevant, sufficiently representative, and to the best extent possible, free of errors and complete". Article 10(3) extends this to require that datasets "take into account the characteristics and limitations of the data, including possible deficiencies such as biases, that might affect human health, safety or fundamental rights". Achieving statistical representativeness across protected characteristics — age, sex, racial or ethnic origin, disability status — typically requires collecting precisely those categories of data that are most tightly restricted under GDPR Article 9.

AI Act Article 10(5) acknowledges this tension by permitting the processing of special-category data for the purposes of bias detection and correction, subject to appropriate technical and organisational measures. However, this permission is narrowly drawn to high-risk AI systems, and its interaction with the GDPR's Article 9 conditions — particularly the absence of an explicit data-subject consent exemption for bias testing — remained a source of operational uncertainty until the 2025 Digital Omnibus proposal introduced a cross-cutting legal basis for processing special categories for bias detection across all AI systems (Rintamaki et al., 2026). That proposal's legislative trajectory is discussed further in Section 6.1.5.

The European Data Protection Board, in Opinion 28/2024 of 17 December 2024, set out a three-step legitimate-interest test specific to AI development and deployment and held that AI models trained on personal data cannot in all cases be considered anonymous: anonymity must be assessed case by case, with both the likelihood of direct extraction and the likelihood of obtaining personal data through queries being "insignificant" (EDPB, 2024). The CNIL's 2026 recommendations supplement this with concrete techniques — federated learning, synthetic data, differential privacy, pseudonymisation (CNIL, 2026). However, EDPB Opinion 28/2024 uses heavily qualified language: the phrase "may" or "might" appears with high frequency throughout, and the document explicitly contemplates case-by-case national interpretation. Cross-jurisdictional uniformity should not be assumed; engineering choices made to satisfy one national supervisor may not satisfy another.

6.1.3 Data Act versus GDPR: Mandatory Sharing Against Purpose Limitation

Articles 4 and 5 of the Data Act establish a default entitlement for users of connected products to access — and to direct the sharing of — the data generated by their use of those products (European Parliament and Council, 2023). Where such co-generated data includes personal data of third parties (for example, passengers in a connected vehicle whose biometric data is captured by an in-cabin monitoring system), Data Act sharing obligations can collide with GDPR's purpose-limitation and lawful-basis requirements. A vehicle fleet operator that generates data involving multiple data subjects cannot simply hand over a bulk dataset in response to a user's Data Act Article 4 request without first satisfying itself that the GDPR basis for the secondary transfer is in place.

The Data Act addresses this tension by affirming GDPR primacy where the two conflict, but the engineering challenge is non-trivial: the data holder must filter, segregate, or pseudonymise personal data of non-users before sharing, while preserving the analytical utility of the dataset. For IoT data streams involving many simultaneous users — a shared workspace sensor grid, a multi-tenant industrial environment, a smart building — this segregation is a non-trivial data-pipeline engineering problem, not a legal interpretation problem.

The Digital Omnibus proposal of November 2025 strengthens trade-secret protections within the Data Act, allowing holders to refuse disclosure where it would cause serious economic damage or pose a high risk of unlawful acquisition by third-country entities. This modification reflects industry concerns that the original Article 4(3) language under-protected confidential information. At the

same time, it introduces a new layer of legal uncertainty: data holders must now assess not only their GDPR obligations and Data Act access obligations, but also whether the trade-secret exemption applies and whether refusing disclosure on those grounds is defensible to both data regulators and supervisory authorities.

6.1.4 DSA versus Trade-Secret Protections

DSA Articles 27 (recommender system parameters), 39 (advertising transparency for very large online platforms), and 40 (researcher access to data) impose progressively deeper algorithmic transparency obligations. These obligations interact with trade-secret protections under the Trade Secrets Directive (Directive (EU) 2016/943) and with the trade-secret-shielding mechanisms now embedded in the revised Data Act. The Stanford Working Paper No. 134 (Prescott, 2026) documents the litigation strategies that very large online platforms have deployed to resist disclosure under Article 39, framing the dispute as a clash between Charter rights and competition-sensitive disclosure. De Noyette, Stähler, and Margoni (2025) coin the term "data secrets" to capture the emerging sub-category of information that is simultaneously regulated data and trade secret, and argue that the Data Act effectively creates a new procedural regime for such hybrid information through competent national authorities and technical protection measures (De Noyette, Stähler and Margoni, 2025; SSRN 5054138).

For compliance tooling, the DSA/trade-secret interaction creates a practically important problem: no automated tool can determine, without human judgment and legal advice, whether a given algorithm or dataset component qualifies as a trade secret and whether the proportionality balance with the DSA transparency obligation is satisfied. The obligation thus sits in a space that automated compliance checking cannot fully inhabit.

6.1.5 AI Act versus Cyber Resilience Act: Double Conformity

An AI system embedded in a product with digital elements falls under both regimes. Article 12 of the CRA, read together with AI Act Article 43 and Recital 78, addresses this by establishing a "conformity presumption": where the CRA's essential cybersecurity requirements (Annex I) are met, the AI Act's Article 15 cybersecurity requirements are deemed satisfied (Taylor Wessing, 2025; Freshfields, 2026). Generally, the AI Act conformity assessment procedure applies and absorbs the CRA cybersecurity assessment. However, for products classified as "important" (CRA Annex III) or "critical" (CRA Annex IV) with digital elements that are also high-risk AI systems, the CRA conformity-assessment route takes precedence for the cybersecurity component.

The Digital Omnibus on AI, provisionally agreed by the Council and Parliament on 7 May 2026 (Consilium, 2026), signalled an intention to make the CRA procedure the primary route for AI-as-product-with-digital-elements and to extend a single-application/single-assessment regime to conformity assessment bodies designated under both instruments, which would substantially reduce the duplication that has emerged in practice. Until that simplification is formally adopted, however, manufacturers of AI systems embedded in hardware products must navigate both

frameworks in parallel, with different notified-body designation regimes and different technical-documentation scopes.

6.1.6 DORA versus NIS2 in the Financial Sector

DORA and NIS2 share architectural goals — ICT risk management, incident reporting, supply-chain oversight — but apply at different depths and granularities. The relationship is governed by the *lex specialis* principle codified in NIS2 Article 4: where DORA addresses an issue with at least equivalent effect, it displaces NIS2 (Clausmeier, 2023). The most operationally consequential divergence is in incident reporting. DORA requires initial notification of a major ICT-related incident within four hours of classification, an intermediate report within 72 hours, and a final report within one month (Joint Committee of the European Supervisory Authorities, 2024). NIS2 requires an early warning within 24 hours, an incident notification within 72 hours, and a final report within one month. For an entity in scope of both, the binding constraint is the four-hour DORA deadline, but reports flow to different competent authorities — financial supervisors under DORA (such as the ECB, BaFin, or ACPR), national CSIRTs or NIS2 competent authorities under NIS2 — using different templates and classification criteria.

The engineering implications are significant. Compliance with the DORA timeline demands real-time incident-classification capability integrated into security operations, pre-prepared report templates auto-populated from telemetry, and dual-submission pipelines targeting both DORA and NIS2 reporting channels. For a financial entity deploying AI in credit scoring or fraud detection — Annex III high-risk under the AI Act — the additional Article 26 deployer obligations (human oversight, logging, monitoring) must be satisfied without disturbing the DORA testing and audit regime. The European Systemic Risk Board (2021) has recommended a pan-European framework for coordinated cross-border response to large-scale incidents, but at the time of writing such a framework is not yet operative.

6.1.7 The Digital Omnibus as Legislative Response

Published on 19 November 2025 as part of the Commission's "Omnibus VII" package, and provisionally agreed by the Council and Parliament on 7 May 2026 in respect of the AI component (Consilium, 2026), the Digital Omnibus targets exactly the tensions catalogued above. Its proposals include: a single incident-reporting platform spanning GDPR, NIS2, and DORA; a 96-hour breach-notification window under GDPR where breaches present a high risk to individuals; an explicit legal basis for processing special categories of personal data for bias detection and correction across all AI systems; consolidation of the Open Data Directive, the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation, and parts of the DGA into the Data Act; a delay of up to sixteen months for the application of high-risk AI obligations; and a streamlined dual-designation regime for AI Act and CRA conformity assessment bodies.

These proposals have attracted substantive criticism. The EDPB and EDPS, in Joint Opinion 2/2026 of 10 February 2026, characterised the proposed changes to the GDPR's personal-data definition as

"going far beyond a technical amendment". German industry associations warned that the Omnibus makes rules "more complicated, creating legal uncertainty" (Quaritsch, 2026). Six Member States including France and Germany opposed the centralised incident-reporting platform, stating that it "could lead to greater complexity". Domínguez de Olazábal (2025), writing in Tech Policy Press, concludes that "the Omnibus introduces complexity instead of clarity." The legislative procedure is ongoing; the GDPR, Data Act, and NIS2 components have not yet been provisionally agreed, and the final text will differ from the November 2025 proposal in material respects. Engineering decisions taken on the assumption that omnibus changes will pass in their current form should be hedged accordingly.

6.2 Multi-Level Governance Challenges

EU digital regulation operates at four layers that engineers must track in parallel. The primary layer is legislation — regulations and directives. The second is harmonised technical standardisation, primarily through CEN/CENELEC for AI Act and CRA standards, ETSI for telecommunications-adjacent areas, and ENISA-produced guidance and certification schemes for cybersecurity. The third is soft law: EDPB guidelines (notably Opinion 28/2024 on AI models, Guidelines 4/2019 on data protection by design and by default, and Guidelines 1/2024 on legitimate interest), European AI Office documents (notably the GPAI Code of Practice published on 10 July 2025, endorsed by the AI Board on 1 August 2025), CJEU case law (such as Case C-413/23 P on pseudonymisation), and informal interpretive bulletins. The fourth layer, for directives, is Member State transposition.

NIS2 illustrates the practical consequences of multi-layer governance with unusual clarity. The transposition deadline of 17 October 2024 was missed by the great majority of Member States. By 7 May 2025 the Commission had issued reasoned opinions to nineteen Member States — including Germany, France, Spain, Poland, the Netherlands, and Sweden — for failure to notify full transposition (European Commission, 2025a). As of mid-2025, only fourteen of the twenty-seven EU Member States had fully transposed NIS2 (specifically: Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Malta, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia) (White & Case LLP, 2025). Substantive divergences have emerged: Italy and Slovenia extended sectoral scope, Belgium added board-level cybersecurity-oversight requirements, and Hungary introduced specific separation rules between CISO and DPO roles (Mikolášik and Pucicov, 2026; ECSO, 2025). For organisations operating cross-border, this means that the technically uniform Article 21 baseline coexists with non-uniform national implementing rules on reporting thresholds, registration deadlines, penalty regimes, and supervisory practice. Compliance tooling must accommodate per-jurisdiction rule sets, not a single EU rule book.

A parallel phenomenon affects the GDPR's already-mature interpretive apparatus. National DPAs interpret Article 6(1)(f) "legitimate interest" and Article 32 "appropriate technical and organisational measures" with non-trivial variation. The Hamburg DPA's 2024 position paper on LLM personal-data status, the Dutch DPA's stricter line on web scraping, and the French CNIL's more permissive legitimate-interest framework for AI development illustrate the resulting interpretive plurality. The 2025 CJEU judgment in C-413/23 P on pseudonymisation, which the Digital Omnibus seeks to codify,

further shifts the personal-data perimeter in ways that national supervisors have not yet uniformly interpreted.

The European AI Office, established within DG CONNECT, now operates as a horizontal governance layer of its own. The GPAI Code of Practice remains formally voluntary, but the Office's guidelines on the scope of obligations for providers of GPAI models (published 18 July 2025) make clear that non-adherence triggers heightened scrutiny — more frequent requests for information and access. For compliance tooling, this layered governance carries three engineering corollaries. First, no single textual artefact can serve as the compliance ground truth; tooling must ingest primary legislation, harmonised standards (some of which, at the time of writing, have not yet been adopted), DPA and AI Office guidance, and CJEU rulings. Second, multi-jurisdictional operation requires per-Member-State rule layers, machine-readable wherever possible. Third, the interpretive state of the framework is dynamic, not static: a tooling decision correct under today's guidance may become incorrect when a new EDPB opinion or CJEU judgment is published.

Figure 6.2. Concurrent incident-notification deadlines triggered by a single event under DORA, NIS2, GDPR, and the proposed Digital Omnibus. From a common point of incident awareness, four separate reporting clocks begin running in parallel, each owed to a different authority and governed by a different instrument: DORA's four-hour initial notification, NIS2's twenty-four-hour early warning, GDPR's seventy-two-hour breach notification, and the Omnibus proposal's prospective ninety-six-hour window for high-risk breaches. The figure illustrates that compliance with the earliest deadline does not discharge the obligations that follow, and that an organisation subject to all four instruments must maintain incident-response procedures capable of meeting each threshold independently.

6.3 Sectoral Specificities and Domain Applications

6.3.1 Healthcare

The healthcare sector is among the most densely regulated under the combined framework. The EHDS Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2025/327, entered into force 5 April 2025) sits on top of a pre-existing layer of GDPR, MDR/IVDR, and NIS2 obligations, and interacts with the AI Act's high-risk

classification for AI systems used in medical diagnosis, treatment decisions, and patient management.

The EHDS introduces a secondary-use access pathway through Health Data Access Bodies: researchers and public-interest actors may request access to health data held by healthcare providers, subject to a Data Permit. However, EHDS-permitted processing is confined to ring-fenced secure processing environments, with identifiable access logs retained for at least one year for audit purposes — a documentary obligation that interacts uneasily with GDPR's storage-limitation principle. The MDR and IVDR post-market surveillance regime requires manufacturers of devices, including AI-as-medical-device, to retain clinical performance data and adverse-event logs throughout the product lifetime, which can extend well beyond the horizon that a strict GDPR Article 17 analysis might impose. A 2025 peer-reviewed analysis confirms that the MDR quality-management system can serve as a foundation for AI Act compliance and that technical documentation requirements can be integrated rather than duplicated (Tandem Health, 2025).

6.3.2 Financial Sector

Beyond the DORA/NIS2 interaction discussed in Section 6.1.6, the financial sector faces a further layer of complexity. DORA's Article 13 ICT risk-management obligations require continuous monitoring of ICT systems, which generates substantial personal data flows (employee identifiers, customer transaction metadata). GDPR breach notification under Article 33 — within 72 hours of becoming aware — runs in parallel with DORA's four-hour major-incident reporting and NIS2's 24-hour early-warning regime, with each clock starting from a differently defined trigger and each report going to a different authority. Where AI is deployed for credit scoring or fraud detection — Annex III high-risk under the AI Act — the financial entity must additionally satisfy Article 26 deployer obligations (human oversight, logging, monitoring) without disturbing the DORA testing and audit regime.

6.3.3 Public Sector

Public deployers of high-risk AI — in law enforcement, asylum, migration, social benefits administration, and education — face a particularly dense regulatory stack. AI Act Article 27 requires deployers that are bodies governed by public law to conduct a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment before first use of a high-risk AI system. This obligation runs in parallel with GDPR Article 35 Data Protection Impact Assessments, national administrative-law procedural requirements, and the Interoperable Europe Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/903, in force from 11 April 2024, with mandatory interoperability assessments applying from 12 January 2025). The Interoperable Europe Act introduces an interoperability assessment that must be carried out before any decision on new or substantially modified binding requirements affecting trans-European digital public services, and mandates sharing of interoperability solutions — including source code and documentation — on request (European Parliament and Council, 2024b). The combined effect is that a public-sector AI deployment now demands at minimum four interlocking ex-ante assessments — DPIA, FRIA,

interoperability assessment, and a security risk assessment under NIS2 Article 21 — which engineers must orchestrate through unified documentation pipelines.

The regulatory interactions catalogued in this chapter are not incidental defects of the EU legislative process; they reflect the reality that the framework was assembled through multiple legislative cycles, by different institutional actors, in response to different perceived problems. From an informatics standpoint, the practitioner implication is clear: compliance cannot be achieved by applying each regulation independently. It requires a systems view in which obligations from all applicable instruments are mapped simultaneously, conflicts are identified early in the design cycle, and architectural decisions are taken with full awareness of their cross-regulatory consequences. Chapter 7 develops the corresponding role analysis — identifying who bears each obligation — while Chapter 8 maps those obligations to the technical tooling landscape and identifies where the tools to satisfy them do not yet exist.

7 ROLES AND OBLIGATIONS CREATED BY THE REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS

The regulatory instruments analysed in Chapters 4 to 6 do not impose obligations on undifferentiated "organisations." They create a structured ecosystem of named roles — each with a specific definition, a specific set of obligations, and a specific set of technical artefacts that must exist and be producible on demand. From an informatics standpoint, these roles are the unit of compliance: a system cannot be assessed as compliant or non-compliant in the abstract; it can only be assessed as compliant or non-compliant with respect to a particular role that a particular actor holds with respect to that system.

This chapter analyses the roles created by the regulatory framework, their technical content, their lifecycle dynamics, and the ambiguities that persist. It then turns to the question of how those roles, and the obligations attached to them, can be represented in machine-readable form — a necessary step both for automated compliance checking and for the interoperable exchange of compliance information across the AI value chain. The vocabulary and metadata standards available for this purpose now form a substantial ecosystem, and mapping that ecosystem is as important a task as mapping the regulatory roles themselves.

7.1 New Technical Roles Introduced by the AI Act

7.1.1 Provider versus Deployer: Technical Distinctions

The AI Act defines a provider in Article 3(3) as a natural or legal person that develops an AI system or has it developed and places it on the market or puts it into service under its own name or trademark. A deployer is defined in Article 3(4) as a natural or legal person using an AI system under their authority, except in a personal or non-professional capacity. The technical significance of the

distinction is that providers carry design-phase obligations — risk management system (Article 9), data governance (Article 10), technical documentation (Article 11 and Annex IV), automatic event logging (Article 12), transparency information for deployers (Article 13), human-oversight design (Article 14), accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity (Article 15), quality management system (Article 17), conformity assessment (Article 43), CE marking, and EU database registration (Article 71). Deployers carry operational obligations: use in accordance with instructions (Article 26(1)), ensure competent human oversight (Article 26(2)), monitor operation and report serious incidents (Article 26(5)), retain automatically generated logs (Article 26(6)), and conduct a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment where applicable (Article 27).

The boundary is not static. Article 25 specifies three reclassification triggers: rebranding a high-risk system under one's own name or trademark; making a substantial modification to a high-risk system; and changing the intended purpose of a non-high-risk system in a way that renders it high-risk. The definition of substantial modification in Article 3(23) — a change not foreseen in the initial conformity assessment that affects compliance with Articles 9 to 15 or alters intended purpose — is technically indeterminate in several important cases. Prompt engineering, RAG patterns, and few-shot configuration are generally treated as non-substantial; full fine-tuning, replacement of the operating environment, and material changes to input/output schema are more likely to qualify. European Commission guidelines on the threshold remain pending at the time of writing.

The technical line between provider and deployer is not always clean in practice. An organisation that purchases a foundation model and builds an application on top of it is, with respect to the foundation model, a deployer; with respect to the application it builds and places on the market or puts into service under its own brand, it is a provider. The provider–deployer distinction thus maps onto system boundaries in technical architectures, and those boundaries must be defined with regulatory precision, not merely for engineering convenience.

7.1.2 The AI System Lifecycle and Role Transitions

Roles can shift across the full AI system lifecycle — development, training, validation, deployment, monitoring, decommissioning — and must therefore be traceable in version-controlled documentation. The GPAI supply chain makes this dynamic most visible. A foundation-model provider under Articles 51–55 supplies a model with documentation under Annexes XI and XII. A downstream fine-tuner may remain a deployer or become a GPAI provider depending on modification magnitude; the European Commission's July 2025 Guidelines on GPAI obligations position the threshold at roughly one-third of the original training compute. An application developer integrating the GPAI model into a high-risk system typically remains a deployer with respect to the underlying model while assuming provider status for the high-risk application built on top.

Beyond substantial modification, the AI Act's role transitions are also triggered by placing on the market, putting into service, and importing, each defined in Articles 3(9)–(11). An importer who brings a high-risk AI system developed outside the EU onto the EU market assumes provider

obligations where the provider has not designated an EU-based authorised representative. A distributor who makes changes to a product bearing a CE mark may similarly be reclassified as a provider. These supply-chain dynamics demand that contract templates between AI developers, deployers, importers, and distributors reflect the regulatory role allocation, and that Article 25(2)–(4) cooperation obligations — particularly the duty of the provider to share information and technical assistance with downstream parties — are operationalised through data-sharing agreements and technical documentation APIs.

The engineering implication is that AI system version control must integrate with regulatory metadata: each release must be tagged not only with code and weights identifiers but with the regulatory role-set it instantiates, the conformity assessment route applicable, and the cooperation obligations owed upstream and downstream under Article 25(2)–(4).

7.1.3 General Purpose AI: Upstream Providers and Downstream Integrators

The AI Act's GPAI provisions (Articles 51–56) introduce a further role layer. A GPAI model provider — an entity that develops and makes available a model with general-purpose capabilities, trained on broad data using large-scale self-supervision (Article 3(63)) — bears transparency, copyright-compliance, and technical-documentation obligations under Article 53. If the model is designated as having systemic risk (Article 51), the provider additionally bears Article 55 obligations: model evaluation per standardised adversarial-testing protocols, incident reporting to the AI Office, cybersecurity safeguards, and energy-efficiency reporting.

For the application developer who fine-tunes the foundation model, the role topology is more complex: GPAI provider upstream, fine-tuner-as-GPAI-provider for the modified model depending on the extent of modification, high-risk system provider for the integrated application, and deployer downstream. Each role transition must be reflected in version-controlled documentation, model cards, datasheets, and conformity records.

7.2 Roles Under Data Regulations

7.2.1 Data Controller and Data Processor Responsibilities

GDPR Article 4(7) defines a controller as the entity that determines the purposes and means of personal data processing; Article 4(8) defines a processor as the entity processing personal data on behalf of the controller. Controllers bear data protection by design and by default obligations (Article 25), must maintain records of processing activities (Article 30), conduct DPIAs for high-risk processing (Article 35), and respond to data subject rights. Processors must implement appropriate technical and organisational measures (Articles 28 and 32) and act only on documented controller instructions.

The controller–processor boundary in cloud-hosted AI systems is persistently contested. A cloud ML platform that ingests training data, chooses model architectures, and exposes inference endpoints

may be a joint controller rather than a processor — depending on how much it shapes the means of processing. EDPB Opinion 28/2024 addresses this only obliquely, emphasising case-by-case assessment and leaving room for significant supervisory divergence across Member States.

Joint controllership, governed by Article 26, imposes a further engineering requirement: the joint controllers must determine their respective responsibilities by agreement, and the arrangement must be made available to data subjects on request. Where an AI system is jointly operated — for example, a data federation in which multiple hospitals contribute patient data to a shared analytical model — the joint-controllership agreement must map onto the technical architecture and specify which party is responsible for access requests, erasure obligations, and breach notifications.

7.2.2 Data Holder, Data User, and Data Intermediary Under the Data Act and DGA

The Data Act introduces a parallel role taxonomy. The Data Act's Article 2(6) defines a "data holder" as any natural or legal person with the right or obligation to use or make available data, with specific application to data generated by connected products and related services. The Data Governance Act's Article 2(8) provides a related but distinct definition — a legal person, including public sector bodies, that has the right to grant access to or to share certain personal or non-personal data, explicitly excluding data subjects with respect to data about themselves. Although the final text of the Data Act partially aligned the definitions, differences in scope and emphasis persist.

A "data user" under the Data Act Article 2(9) is a legal or natural person who has lawful access to certain data and is entitled to use that data for commercial or non-commercial purposes. A "data intermediary" under the DGA Articles 10–15 is an entity providing data-sharing services between data holders and data users, subject to a notification regime, structural separation requirements, and a prohibition on using intermediated data for any purpose beyond improving the intermediation service. This prohibition has direct engineering consequences: a data intermediary cannot repurpose the traffic flowing through its platform for its own analytics, advertising, or product development, and its architecture must enforce this constraint through access controls and purpose-tagging mechanisms.

7.2.3 Data Protection Officer: Technical Expectations

GDPR Article 37 requires the designation of a Data Protection Officer where processing is carried out by a public authority, where core activities consist of regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale, or where core activities consist of large-scale processing of special categories of data. The DPO's technical role under Articles 38 and 39 is to monitor compliance, advise on DPIAs (Article 35), advise on appropriate technical and organisational measures, and act as the contact point for the supervisory authority. Effective DPO oversight presupposes access to a defined set of technical artefacts: data flow diagrams, system architecture documentation, model cards for AI systems processing personal data, retention and deletion schedules, audit logs of personal-data processing activities, and the Article 30 records of processing activities.

Where AI systems are involved, the DPO must additionally have access to bias-evaluation results, accuracy metrics, and documentation of human-oversight procedures — a substantial expansion of the traditional DPO toolkit that has no precedent in the pre-AI GDPR compliance ecosystem. Organisations developing or deploying AI systems should therefore treat DPO access to AI system documentation as a first-class architectural requirement, not an afterthought.

7.2.4 Data Intermediaries and Altruism Organisations

The DGA creates two further role categories. Data intermediaries (Chapter II, Articles 10–15) provide commercial data-sharing services between data holders and data users and must operate on a basis of neutrality — not using data for any purpose other than to make it available to data users, and being functionally separated from any other services they provide. Data altruism organisations (Articles 16–25) collect data donations for objectives of general interest (scientific research, combating climate change, improving public health) on a not-for-profit basis, must be functionally separated from any for-profit activities, and may use the common European data altruism consent form once adopted by the Commission. Both roles generate specific technical obligations: data intermediaries must implement access control, audit logging, and interoperability with participants; data altruism organisations must register and maintain consent records using the standard form.

The IDS Connector architecture — the primary technical instantiation of a data intermediary — maps closely to the DGA's functional requirements. The IDSA Usage Control Language (an ODRL profile) allows permissions, prohibitions, and obligations to be expressed programmatically across 21 policy classes, but enforcement depends on participant honesty and certified infrastructure — a dependency discussed further in Section 7.6 and in Chapter 8.

7.3 Roles Under Cybersecurity Regulations

7.3.1 Operators of Essential Services and Important Entities

NIS2 Article 3 distinguishes essential entities (Annex I sectors, plus large entities in Annex II sectors) from important entities (medium-sized entities in Annexes I and II). Both categories bear identical substantive obligations under Article 21 — risk analysis, incident handling, business continuity, supply-chain security, vulnerability handling, multi-factor authentication, encryption, and access control — but essential entities are subject to ex ante and ex post supervision while important entities face only ex post supervision. The incident reporting obligation under Article 23 runs across three stages: an early warning within 24 hours, a full incident notification within 72 hours, and a final report within one month. Meeting these timelines requires real-time SIEM and EDR capability, automated alerting, incident-classification playbooks, and integration with national CSIRT submission channels.

7.3.2 Manufacturers and Importers Under the CRA

The Cyber Resilience Act defines manufacturers, importers, and distributors. Manufacturers bear the bulk of substantive obligations: security by design and by default (Annex I Part I), vulnerability handling (Annex I Part II), reporting actively exploited vulnerabilities to ENISA within 24 hours (Article 14), maintaining a Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) in a commonly used and machine-readable format (Article 13(6)), conformity assessment (Article 32), CE marking, and retention of technical documentation for at least ten years. The SBOM obligation has been operationalised most concretely by Germany's BSI TR-03183-2 (August 2025), which specifies CycloneDX 1.6+ or SPDX 3.0.1+ in JSON or XML, recursive first-level dependencies, SHA-512 hashes, SPDX licence identifiers, and recommended digital signing.

7.4 Mapping of Roles and Corresponding Responsibilities

To consolidate the role analysis above into a single reference, Table 7.1 maps each role identified in Sections 7.1–7.3 to its source regulation, typical role-holder, core obligations, key article references, and the technical artefacts that must exist and be producible on demand.

Table 7.1. Regulatory roles created across the AI Act, GDPR, the Data Act, the DGA, NIS2, the CRA, and DORA, mapped to their typical role-holders, core obligations, governing articles, required technical artefacts, and the engineering implications each role generates. The table shows that a single organisation routinely holds several of these roles simultaneously — most starkly the public-sector AI deployer, who must satisfy four interlocking ex-ante assessments under three separate instruments before a system can be deployed — and that the technical artefacts demanded by each role (logs, SBOMs, DPIAs, conformity declarations, model cards) form a documentation set that compliance tooling must treat as a single, cross-referenced graph rather than as instrument-by-instrument checklists.

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
Provider (high-risk AI)	AI Act	Developer or brand-owner placing a high-risk AI system on the EU market	Risk management system; data governance and quality; technical documentation; automatic event logging; transparency to deployer; human oversight measures; accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity; conformity assessment; QMS; EU database registration; post-market monitoring	Arts. 9–17, 49, 72; Annex IV	Annex IV technical documentation; risk management records; event logs; conformity declaration; QMS documentation; post-market monitoring plan; model card	Design-phase: embed risk management and logging from day one. Version control must include regulatory metadata per release. Conformity assessment required before market placement.
Deployer (high-risk AI)	AI Act	Organisation or individual using a high-risk AI system	Implement instructions for use; monitor operation; report	Arts. 26(1), 26(5), 26(6), 26(7), 27	Operational logs (minimum retention period); incident reports;	Must not modify system in a way that triggers reclassification as

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
		under their authority	serious incidents; conduct Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (public bodies); inform affected persons in specified contexts; maintain logs for minimum period		FRIA documentation; internal instructions-for-use records	provider (see Art. 25). Needs override mechanism and escalation procedure for human oversight.
Distributor	AI Act	Entity in the supply chain making a high-risk AI system available on the EU market without placing it	Verify CE marking and conformity declaration; ensure instructions and information are provided; store and transport without compromising compliance	Art. 24	CE marking records; conformity declaration copies	Modification of a CE-marked product triggers reclassification as provider. Contracts must clarify role allocation.
Importer	AI Act	Entity established in the EU placing a system from a	Verify conformity; ensure provider has EU authorised	Art. 23	Conformity verification records;	Assumes provider obligations if provider has no EU

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
		non-EU provider on the EU market	representative; affix importer details to system; report non-conforming systems		authorised representative designation	representative. Due diligence on upstream providers is legally required.
GPAI Model Provider (general)	AI Act	Entity developing and making available a general-purpose AI model	Technical documentation; copyright-compliance policy; transparency to downstream providers; summary of training data	Art. 53; Annex XI, XII	Model card; technical documentation (Annex XI); training data summary; copyright policy documentation	Must disclose sufficient information for downstream integrators to meet their own obligations. Cooperation with downstream providers is mandatory.
GPAI Model Provider (systemic risk)	AI Act	Provider of a GPAI model with systemic risk ($\geq 10^{25}$ FLOPs training compute)	All Art. 53 obligations; model evaluation per standardised adversarial-testing protocols; incident	Arts. 51, 55; GPAI Code of Practice (July 2025)	Safety and Security Framework documentation; adversarial testing records; incident reports; energy	Compliance with Art. 55(1)(a) currently requires judgment under uncertainty — standardised

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
		or designated by AI Office)	reporting to AI Office; cybersecurity safeguards; energy-efficiency reporting		consumption data; model evaluation results	protocols not yet settled. Estimated compliance cost: €5M–€15M/year per model.
Data Controller	GDPR	Entity determining purposes and means of personal data processing	Data protection by design and by default; lawful basis for all processing; DPIA for high-risk processing; respond to data subject rights (access, rectification, erasure, portability); breach notification within 72 hours; records of processing activities	Arts. 5, 6, 24, 25, 30, 32, 33, 35	Article 30 RoPA; DPIAs; privacy notices; consent records; breach notification logs; data flow diagrams; deletion/retention schedules	Must map all data flows and purposes. For AI systems, RoPA must include model-training and inference activities. Joint-controllership agreements required where applicable.

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
Data Processor	GDPR	Entity processing personal data on behalf of a controller	Process only on documented controller instructions; implement appropriate technical and organisational measures; assist controller with data subject rights and breach notification; delete or return data on termination	Arts. 28, 29, 32	Data Processing Agreement (DPA); security measure documentation; sub-processor records; breach notification procedures	Cloud ML platforms and AI inference services are likely processors (or joint controllers if they shape means of processing). DPA must specify subject matter, duration, nature, and purpose.
Data Protection Officer (DPO)	GDPR	Designated individual (internal or external) overseeing GDPR compliance	Monitor compliance; advise on DPIAs; advise on technical and organisational measures; act as supervisory authority contact point	Arts. 37–39	Access to: data flow diagrams; system architecture docs; model cards; audit logs; retention schedules; Article 30 RoPA; bias	DPO must have access to AI system documentation as a first-class architectural requirement. Where AI processes personal

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
					evaluation results; accuracy metrics	data, DPO role expands to include ML-specific artefacts.
Data Holder	Data Act	Any natural or legal person with the right or obligation to use or make available data, typically a manufacturer or related service provider for connected-product data	Grant users access to data generated by connected products; share data with third parties on user instruction; not use data to derive competing insights against users; comply with data portability obligations	Art. 2(6); Arts. 3–6, Data Act	Data access interfaces; data portability APIs; data-sharing agreements; GDPR-compliant filtering mechanisms for third-party personal data	Must separate personal data of non-consenting third parties before sharing. Trade-secret exemption (strengthened by Digital Omnibus 2025) may justify refusal of disclosure in specific cases.
Data Holder	DGA	Legal person or public sector body with the right to grant access to personal or non-personal data	Enable access to data for re-use under applicable conditions; not discriminate between data re-	Art. 2(8), DGA	Data access logs; re-use agreements; technical access interfaces	Definition differs from the Data Act's broader Art. 2(6) data holder — DGA applies only to legal

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
		(excluding data subjects re: their own data)	users in comparable situations			persons/public bodies and excludes data subjects. Organisations subject to both must track which definition applies to each data asset.
Data User	Data Act	Legal or natural person with lawful access to data entitled to use it	Use data only in accordance with agreed conditions and applicable law; not use data to create competing products against the data holder	Art. 2(9), Data Act	Data use agreements; purpose-logging mechanisms	Downstream use is contractually and technically constrained. Usage control policies (ODRL-based) should be embedded at the point of access.
Data Intermediary	DGA	Entity providing commercial data-sharing services between data	Notification to competent authority; structural separation from	Arts. 10–15, DGA	Notification records; structural separation documentation; purpose-tagging	Architecture must technically enforce the prohibition on repurposing intermediated

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
		holders and data users	other services; prohibition on using intermediated data for own purposes; neutrality obligations		and access control architecture; audit logs of data flows	data. IDS Connector implementations are the current closest technical analogue.
Data Altruism Organisation	DGA	Recognised not-for-profit entity collecting data for general-interest purposes	Not-for-profit operation; functional separation from for-profit activities; use of European data altruism consent form (when available); registration in national register	Arts. 16–25, DGA	Registration records; consent records using European form; functional separation documentation	Business model must be structured to preclude for-profit benefit from altruism data. Dual-use with commercial services is prohibited at the structural level.
Essential Entity	NIS2	Large entities in Annex I high-criticality sectors	Risk analysis and information security policies;	Art. 21, NIS2	Security policies; incident-response playbooks;	Subject to ex ante and ex post supervisory

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
		(energy, transport, banking, health, digital infrastructure, etc.)	incident handling; business continuity; supply-chain security; vulnerability handling; cryptography; MFA/continuous authentication; staff training		business continuity plans; supply-chain risk assessments; vulnerability disclosure records; SIEM/EDR telemetry	oversight. Telemetry retention for 18 months (common guidance). Data costs increase 3–10x vs baseline MDR services.
Important Entity	NIS2	Medium-sized entities in Annex I/II sectors, and specifically designated entities	Same substantive obligations as essential entities under Art. 21	Art. 21, NIS2	Same artefacts as essential entities	Subject only to ex post supervision. Same technical obligations apply; supervisory intensity differs.
NIS2 Incident Reporter	NIS2	Essential and important entities	Early warning within 24 h; incident notification within 72 h; final report within 1 month	Art. 23, NIS2	Automated alerting pipeline; pre-populated report templates; CSIRT submission integration; incident	Must run in parallel with DORA 4-hour and GDPR 72-hour notification obligations where applicable. Unified

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
					classification playbooks	incident-response procedure recommended.
Manufacturer (products with digital elements)	CRA	Entity developing and placing on the market software or hardware products with digital elements	Security by design and by default; vulnerability handling throughout support period; report actively exploited vulnerabilities to ENISA within 24 h; SBOM (machine-readable, top-level dependencies minimum); conformity assessment; CE marking; retain technical documentation ≥10 years	Arts. 13, 14, 32; Annex I Parts I–II; Annex VIII	SBOM (CycloneDX 1.6+ or SPDX 3.0.1+); vulnerability disclosure records; ENISA incident reports; technical documentation; conformity declaration; CE marking records	AI systems embedded in hardware products fall under both CRA and AI Act. CRA conformity assessment takes precedence for cybersecurity components of important/critical products. Digital Omnibus (May 2026) intends single-assessment regime.

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
Importer (CRA)	CRA	Entity established in the EU placing a CRA-covered product from a non-EU manufacturer on the EU market	Verify manufacturer compliance; ensure technical documentation and instructions available; affix importer details; report non-compliant products	Art. 19, CRA	Compliance verification records; importer labelling documentation	Inherits manufacturer-level obligations if manufacturer cannot be identified or has no EU representative.
Distributor (CRA)	CRA	Entity in the supply chain making a CRA-covered product available without placing it on the market	Verify CE marking; ensure required documentation accompanies product; not modify product in a way that affects compliance	Art. 20, CRA	CE marking verification records	Modification triggers reclassification as manufacturer.
Financial Entity (ICT risk management)	DORA	Credit institutions, investment firms, insurance undertakings,	ICT risk management framework; continuous	Arts. 5–15, 17–23, DORA	ICT risk management policy; continuous monitoring	DORA displaces NIS2 where it applies with equivalent effect

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
		crypto-asset service providers, and others listed in Art. 2	monitoring; ICT-related incident classification and reporting (4 h initial / 72 h intermediate / 1 month final); third-party ICT provider management; DORA-compliant testing including threat-led penetration testing		telemetry; incident reports (to financial supervisors); TLPT documentation; third-party ICT contracts	(lex specialis). Reports go to financial supervisors (ECB, BaFin, ACPR, etc.), not CSIRTs. 4-hour clock is binding constraint where both DORA and NIS2 apply.
Public-Sector AI Deployer	AI Act + GDPR + Interoperable Europe Act	Bodies governed by public law deploying high-risk AI systems	All deployer obligations under AI Act Art. 26; Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment before first use (Art. 27); DPIA (GDPR Art. 35); interoperability assessment before	AI Act Art. 27; GDPR Art. 35; IEA Arts. 3–4	FRIA; DPIA; interoperability assessment report; security risk assessment (NIS2 Art. 21); shared interoperability solution documentation	Minimum four interlocking ex-ante assessments before deployment. Documentation pipelines must be unified across instruments to avoid duplication and inconsistency.

Role	Regulation	Typical Role-Holder	Core Obligations	Key Articles	Technical Artefacts Required	Engineering Implications
			new/modified trans-European digital public services; share interoperability solutions on request			

Notes on Role Dynamics

Roles are not static. Several provisions trigger reclassification that carries the full obligation set of a more demanding role:

- A **deployer** becomes a **provider** if it makes a substantial modification to a high-risk AI system (AI Act Art. 25), changes its intended purpose, or places it on the market under its own brand.
- A **distributor or importer** becomes a **manufacturer** under the CRA if it modifies a product bearing a CE mark.
- A **processor** may be reclassified as a **joint controller** under GDPR if it materially shapes the means of processing (e.g., choosing model architectures or retention policies).
- A **fine-tuner** of a GPAI model may become a **GPAI provider** for the modified model depending on the extent of modification.

Organisations routinely hold multiple roles simultaneously. A hospital deploying an AI-based triage system is simultaneously a GDPR controller, an NIS2 essential entity (health sector), an AI Act deployer of a high-risk system, an EHDS data holder, and potentially an MDR manufacturer if it modifies a medical device. Compliance governance must be structured at the level of the full role topology, not instrument by instrument.

Terminology is inconsistent across instruments. "Data holder" is defined differently in the Data Act and the DGA. "User" has different referents across regulations. "Operator" in the AI Act is a superordinate term that is functionally hollow — substantive obligations remain role-specific. Engineering documentation should always specify the precise regulatory definition being applied.

7.5 Implications for Engineers and Data Architects

7.5.1 Design-Phase Obligations

The regulatory framework imposes a coherent set of design-phase obligations whose cumulative force substantially exceeds the sum of its individual parts. Privacy by design (GDPR Article 25) demands data minimisation embedded in data models from the outset. Security by design (CRA Annex I Part I and NIS2 Article 21) demands threat modelling, secure defaults, attack-surface minimisation, and the application of secure development lifecycles such as ISO/IEC 27034 or the OWASP Software Assurance Maturity Model. The AI Act adds risk management (Article 9), data governance including representativeness and bias mitigation (Article 10), technical documentation (Article 11 and Annex IV), and transparency design (Article 13).

These obligations are not independent checklists; they are concurrent architectural constraints that must be satisfied simultaneously. A system that achieves AI Act Article 10 representativeness through demographic stratification but violates GDPR Article 9 special-category restrictions on the same data is non-compliant in one regime. A system that satisfies GDPR pseudonymisation requirements at a level that destroys the analytical signal needed for AI Act Article 15 accuracy is

non-compliant in the other. The engineering task is to identify architectures that satisfy all constraints concurrently and to document that they do so for each applicable instrument.

7.5.2 Operational and Monitoring Obligations

Continuous monitoring is now a horizontal expectation across the framework. AI Act Article 72 requires providers of high-risk AI to implement post-market monitoring; Article 26(5) requires deployers to monitor operation and to suspend use where the system presents a risk. NIS2 Article 21 requires ongoing incident-detection capability. DORA Article 13 requires continuous ICT-system monitoring with documented detection thresholds. AI Act Article 14 requires that human overseers be genuinely able to understand system outputs, detect anomalies, and intervene or halt operation — an obligation that is aspirationally clear but technically indeterminate for complex deep-learning systems, as detailed in Chapter 8.

At the engineering level, the minimum viable implementation of human oversight involves clearly defined override mechanisms, training requirements for human overseers, logging of override events, and documented escalation procedures. The substantive question — whether the human overseer genuinely understands the system well enough to exercise meaningful judgment — is a research problem, not just an engineering one.

7.5.3 Documentation and Audit Trail Responsibilities

Documentation obligations are pervasive and role-differentiated across the regulatory framework. AI Act Annex IV specifies the minimum content of technical documentation for high-risk AI systems: a general description, a detailed description of system elements and development process, information on training methodology and techniques, results of testing, and a post-market monitoring plan. GDPR Article 30 requires records of processing activities that describe, for each processing operation, the controller identity, purposes, data categories, recipient categories, and retention periods. CRA Article 13 requires documentation sufficient to demonstrate conformity and retained for the product support period or ten years, whichever is longer. NIS2 Article 23 requires incident reports. DORA Article 13 requires documentation of ICT risk management policies, procedures, and testing.

For an organisation simultaneously holding multiple roles — AI Act deployer, GDPR controller, NIS2 essential entity, CRA manufacturer — these obligations are multiplicative. A financial institution deploying a high-risk AI system for credit scoring must maintain, simultaneously: AI Act Annex IV technical documentation, GDPR Article 30 records of processing activities, a DPIA under Article 35, a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment under AI Act Article 27, a DORA ICT risk-management policy covering the system, NIS2 incident-response records, and CRA technical documentation if the system components fall within CRA scope. Engineering practice should treat these as a unified documentation graph, maintained in a version-controlled repository, with cross-references between artefacts and structured so that any single supervisory authority request can be responded to by extracting the relevant subgraph.

7.5 Gaps and Ambiguities in Role Definition

Three persistent ambiguities merit explicit attention.

First, terminology is inconsistent across instruments. "Data holder" is defined differently in the Data Act and the DGA — the Data Act's definition in Article 2(6) covers any natural or legal person with the right or obligation to use or make available data, while the DGA's Article 2(8) definition applies only to legal persons and public sector bodies and explicitly excludes data subjects with respect to their own data. "User" has different referents across regulations. "Operator" in the AI Act is a superordinate term covering providers, deployers, importers, and distributors, but carries no substantive obligations itself. Documentation should always specify the precise regulatory definition being applied.

Second, a single entity routinely holds multiple roles simultaneously. A hospital deploying an AI-based triage system is simultaneously a GDPR controller, an NIS2 essential entity in the health sector, an AI Act deployer of a high-risk system, an EHDS data holder, and potentially an MDR manufacturer if it modifies the device. Compliance governance must be structured at the level of the full role topology, not instrument by instrument. Data-space architectures compound this difficulty: the technical role of an IDS Connector operator maps imperfectly onto controller, processor, data intermediary, and data holder, and the legal allocation depends on the contractual configuration of each connector instance.

Third, two regulatory gaps are particularly visible. The AI Act's open-source carve-out in Article 2(12) is narrowly drawn — GPAI models with systemic risk remain subject to Article 55 regardless of their licence, and open-source components integrated into high-risk systems generate provider obligations at the integration point. The open-source community has expressed concern that the carve-out's narrowness will chill open release of capable models. The academic research exemption in Article 2(8) does not clearly address dual-use research projects that generate deployable model artefacts, leaving a compliance gap for university AI research with external application.

7.6 Representing Roles and Obligations in Machine-Readable Form

The obligations and roles described above impose not only design-time constraints but also documentation requirements that must be expressed in interoperable, machine-readable formats if they are to support automated compliance checking, auditing, and cross-actor information exchange along the AI value chain. A substantial and growing ecosystem of vocabulary standards, ontologies, metadata formats, and policy languages has emerged to address this need. The following subsections survey that ecosystem, noting both its contributions and its current limits.

7.6.1 The Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)

The Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV), developed and maintained by the W3C Data Privacy Vocabularies and Controls Community Group (DPVCG) and now in version 2.0 (Pandit et al., 2024c), provides a comprehensive, machine-readable vocabulary for representing personal data processing activities. Its core covers processing purposes, legal bases, data categories, processing operations, technical and organisational measures, and the roles of controllers, processors, and data subjects. Extensions address specific jurisdictions and regulations: the EU-GDPR extension captures GDPR-specific concepts such as lawful bases under Article 6, special-category conditions under Article 9, and data subject rights under Articles 15–22; an AI Act extension has been developed that covers AI Act roles, risk categories, and documentation concepts.

DPV is expressed in RDF/SKOS and OWL, and can be used alongside other standards — particularly W3C ODRL and SHACL — to support policy expression and validation respectively. Its primary use cases include legal compliance documentation, consent representation (including ISO/IEC TS 27560:2023 consent records for GDPR and the DGA), records of processing activities under GDPR Article 30, and Data Protection Impact Assessments. A DPCat specification (Ryan, Brennan, and Pandit, 2022) extends DPV with DCAT to produce interoperable, machine-readable data processing catalogues compliant with GDPR Article 30. DPV also supports the representation of DGA data-sharing conditions, providing a vocabulary that extends across both the personal-data and non-personal-data governance regimes.

DPV's principal characteristic as a documentation standard is that it records legally and compliance-relevant information rather than verifying or enforcing the legal positions it records. Annotating a dataset's metadata to indicate that processing is grounded in GDPR Article 6(1)(b) (performance of a contract) is a documentation act, not a legal determination: the annotation records the controller's claimed lawful basis but neither confirms that a contract exists nor that the processing falls within its scope. Establishing whether the documented position is legally sound requires additional tooling — SHACL-based shape constraints for structural validation of whether required fields are present and correctly formed, rule engines for logical inference over the documented obligations, or, ultimately, manual legal audit. DPV is not meant to express the complete compliance state.

DPV is, of course, not the only ontology-based approach to legal knowledge representation, and the broader landscape from which it has emerged is worth acknowledging. The legal knowledge representation literature has produced a series of more general frameworks that pre-date and inform the current EU-specific vocabulary ecosystem. Hoekstra, Breuker, Di Bello, and Boer's Legal Knowledge Interchange Format (LKIF), developed under the EU ESTRELLA project, provided an OWL-DL and SWRL foundation for interchanging legal knowledge across heterogeneous systems and remains the canonical reference for upper-level legal ontology design (Hoekstra et al., 2007; Hoekstra et al., 2009). Francesconi's provision model formalises normative provisions in terms of Hohfeldian legal fundamental relations — rights, duties, powers, liabilities — using OWL 2 DL, enabling SPARQL-based reasoning over legislative documents while keeping computational complexity within description-logic tractability (Francesconi, 2016); a later extension demonstrated

that this approach can support defeasible norm reasoning and compliance-checking patterns directly in linked open data environments (Francesconi and Governatori, 2022). Palmirani, Martoni, Rossi, Bartolini, and Robaldo's PrOnto ontology applies a comparable deontic-logic framework specifically to the GDPR, modelling data, actors, processing workflows, purposes, legal bases, and normative obligations to support automated GDPR compliance checking (Palmirani et al., 2018). These frameworks share DPV's ambition — machine-readable legal knowledge — but diverge in emphasis: LKIF and Francesconi's provision model target general legal reasoning across any legislative instrument, PrOnto targets GDPR compliance checking with deontic inference, while DPV prioritises practical interoperability and incremental adoption over formal completeness. The choice to use DPV in the HARNES project reflects this balance: DPV's explicit design for embedding alongside ODRL and SHACL, its alignment with W3C community standards, and its growing adoption across EU data infrastructure make it the most tractable starting point for the cross-regulatory, multi-instrument vocabulary substrate that Chapter 7 identifies as the principal remaining gap.

7.6.2 ODRL and Its Regulatory Profiles

The Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) is a W3C Recommendation (2018) that provides a policy expression framework for stating permissions, prohibitions, and obligations with respect to assets. Its information model structures policies as sets of rules — permissions to perform actions on targets, prohibitions on actions, and obligations that must be fulfilled — attributed to parties (assigners and assignees) and conditionable on constraints (time windows, geographic locations, purpose limitations, usage counts).

ODRL's relevance to EU data regulation is substantial in two distinct contexts. In data spaces, the IDSA has adopted ODRL as the core standard for describing usage policies for data assets, extending it with the IDS Usage Control Language to cover 21 policy classes that map to regulatory constraints including purpose limitation, geographic restriction, data deletion obligations, audit logging requirements, and anonymisation mandates. Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC), the predominant open-source data space connector implementation, operationalises ODRL-based policies at the point of data transfer, encoding them in contract definitions that data consumers must accept before receiving data. This architecture provides the primary technical implementation pathway for Data Act and DGA data-sharing obligations.

In the AI and GDPR compliance domain, ODRL has been combined with DPV to express regulatory policies in a jurisdiction-aware manner. Pandit and Esteves (2024b) demonstrate this combination in the health-data context, using ODRL to encode Data Use Ontology (DUO) concepts and DPV to add GDPR-specific privacy metadata, enabling automated matching between dataset availability conditions and researcher access requests. The ODRL Compliance Profile, proposed by Kirrane et al. (2019), demonstrates that ODRL combined with DPV can achieve effective coverage of GDPR's normative structure.

ODRL's central limitation for regulatory compliance is that it expresses obligations declaratively but does not provide cryptographic enforcement. A connector that receives an ODRL policy stating "data

must be deleted after 30 days" cannot guarantee that the data consumer will honour the obligation; the enforcement is contractual and reputational, not technical. This is the usage-control enforcement gap discussed in Chapter 8.

7.6.3 Croissant: Machine-Readable Dataset Metadata for ML

Croissant (Akhtar et al., 2024) is a metadata format for machine learning datasets, built on schema.org and expressed in JSON-LD. It organises dataset description across four layers: Dataset Metadata (licensing, citation, general provenance), Resource (individual files and file sets), Structure (organisation and format of records, supporting interoperability across modalities), and Semantic (train/test/validation splits and feature-level annotations for practical reuse). It has been adopted as the standard dataset metadata format by major ML repositories including Hugging Face, Kaggle, Dataverse, and OpenML.

For AI Act purposes, Croissant's relevance is direct: AI Act Article 10 requires that providers of high-risk AI systems document the characteristics of training, validation, and testing datasets — provenance, collection methodology, labelling process, known limitations and biases, distribution across relevant subgroups, and measures taken to address identified deficiencies. Croissant's Dataset Metadata layer addresses provenance and licensing; its responsible AI (RAI) extension addresses the documentation of fairness-relevant characteristics including demographic distributions, sensitive attributes, and known biases. This RAI extension provides a structured, interoperable substrate for the Annex IV technical documentation requirements relating to training data — a function that was previously performed only through unstructured datasheets (Gebru et al., 2021) or model cards (Mitchell et al., 2019).

Croissant's limitations from a compliance perspective are also clear. It is a metadata standard, not a verification mechanism: a Croissant file that records a dataset as "demographically balanced across five protected characteristics" does not verify that claim. The format also currently lacks extensions for documenting data retention schedules, data subject consent records, or GDPR lawful bases — information that would be required for full AI Act Article 10 and GDPR Article 30 compliance documentation. Integration with DPV is the natural path for filling these gaps, and such integration is technically feasible given both standards' use of JSON-LD and RDF.

7.6.4 AI-Specific Ontologies: AIRO, VAIR, TAIR, and AICat

Several ontologies have been developed specifically to represent AI Act concepts in machine-readable form. The AI Risk Ontology (AIRO), developed by Golpayegani, Pandit, and Lewis (2022, updated for the final AI Act text), provides an OWL2 representation of AI system risks aligned with AI Act requirements and ISO/IEC 23894 (AI risk management) and ISO 31000. AIRO assists in determining whether a system qualifies as high-risk under Annex III, in maintaining and documenting risk information, and in performing impact assessments. It is designed for use in self-assessment and third-party auditing workflows.

The Vocabulary of AI Risks (VAIR) complements AIRO with a broader taxonomy of AI-related harms and risks, intended to support risk assessment across a wider range of regulatory and ethical frameworks than the AI Act alone. The Trustworthy AI Requirements Ontology (TAIR, 2024) models AI Act clauses alongside ISO management system standards, providing a cross-mapping that allows organisations to identify where ISO 42001 certification provides evidence toward AI Act obligations and where gaps remain.

AICat (Golpayegani et al., 2024b) extends DCAT version 3 to produce a machine-readable catalogue format for AI systems and models, aligned with the AI Act's EU database registration requirement under Article 71. AICat reuses AIRO and DPV concepts, enabling catalogue entries that carry risk classification, provider identity, conformity assessment status, and links to technical documentation artefacts. It mirrors the approach already operational for public-sector open data through DCAT-AP, applying the same interoperability paradigm to the AI system registry.

7.6.5 LegalRuleML, SHACL, and Formal Constraint Validation

Where the vocabulary standards above provide what to record, LegalRuleML and SHACL address how to verify that what is recorded is complete, consistent, and satisfies regulatory requirements.

LegalRuleML is an OASIS standard that extends RuleML to encode legal norms — obligations, permissions, prohibitions, and exceptions — in an XML-based serialisation that preserves their temporal and defeasible characteristics. It was designed specifically to enable the interchange of machine-readable legal rules across systems, with support for normative conflict detection, deontic modalities, and jurisdictional metadata. Its use in AI and data regulation contexts includes the DAOnt ontology for the EU Data Act (Leyva-Sanchez et al., 2026), which encodes Articles 4(1), 8(6), and 19(2)(a) in LegalRuleML-compatible form to enable automated reasoning over data-sharing agreement compliance.

SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) is a W3C Recommendation for validating RDF graphs against a set of conditions expressed as shapes. In the regulatory compliance context, SHACL shapes can encode the structural requirements of a compliant artefact — for example, that a GDPR Article 30 record must include fields for processing purposes, data categories, and retention periods, that an AI Act Annex IV technical documentation set must include a description of training methodology, or that a high-risk AI system registry entry must contain a valid conformity declaration reference. SHACL-based compliance checking has been demonstrated for GDPR (Kirrane et al., 2019), for the AI Act risk management documentation workflow (Golpayegani et al., 2024, using AIRO and VAIR), and for the Data Act (Leyva-Sanchez, 2026). SHACL operates on the closed-world assumption and is therefore suitable for structural validation — verifying that required fields are present and correctly typed — but not for semantic validation of whether the substantive content is accurate.

The AI Cards framework (Golpayegani et al., 2024), developed at Dublin City University and aligned with the HARNES project's scope, combines DPV, AIRO, and DCAT to produce machine-readable AI

and risk documentation aligned with AI Act requirements. AI Cards use SPARQL queries to verify compliance-relevant properties — for example, whether a risk management record documents a mitigation measure for a particular fundamental right impact — and ODRL to express permitted uses of the documented AI system. The framework demonstrates that the individual vocabulary components described in this section can be composed into an integrated compliance documentation workflow, though it also illustrates the current state of the art's principal limitation: each component addresses a slice of the regulatory obligation set, and no integrated cross-regulation compliance substrate yet exists.

7.6.6 Dataset Cataloguing Standards: DCAT, DCAT-AP, and MLDCAT-AP

The Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT), maintained as a W3C Recommendation (version 3, 2024), provides a standard for describing datasets and data services in a catalogue. Its EU application profile, DCAT-AP (version 3.0, 2024), is the mandatory format for the European Data Portal and has been adopted across EU Member State open-data portals. For AI Act and Data Act compliance, DCAT-AP metadata attached to training datasets provides a mechanism for recording provenance, licence, publisher, and spatial and temporal coverage in a way that is interoperable across EU data infrastructure.

MLDCAT-AP (version 2.0, 2024), developed by the EU's SEMIC community, extends DCAT-AP specifically for machine learning datasets, adding properties for dataset type (training, validation, test), modality (image, text, tabular, time series), task (classification, regression, generation), and quality indicators. MLDCAT-AP bridges the gap between DCAT-AP's open-data provenance focus and Croissant's ML-readiness focus, providing an EU-infrastructure-aligned metadata format for the AI Act Article 10 dataset documentation obligation.

7.6.7 The Ecosystem as a Whole: Complementarity and Gaps

The vocabulary and metadata ecosystem described above is extensive but not yet integrated. DPV addresses personal data processing roles and obligations; ODRL addresses policy expression and usage control; Croissant and MLDCAT-AP address ML dataset documentation; AIRO, VAIR, and TAIR address AI risk representation; AICat addresses AI system cataloguing; LegalRuleML addresses formal norm encoding; and SHACL addresses structural validation. Each standard addresses a specific slice of the compliance documentation problem.

What does not yet exist is a unified compliance substrate that integrates these components across instruments. A provider of a high-risk AI system processing personal data in a data space context must simultaneously maintain AI Act Annex IV documentation (addressable through AICat + AIRO + AI Cards), GDPR Article 30 records (addressable through DPV + DPCat), training dataset documentation (addressable through Croissant + MLDCAT-AP), data-sharing policy expressions (addressable through ODRL + IDS-UCL), and structural validation of all of the above (addressable through SHACL). The integration between these components must currently be engineered on a project-by-project basis; no standard integration profile or conformance specification exists.

Developing such a profile — a machine-readable multi-regulation compliance documentation specification that ties together the existing vocabulary components — is one of the most practically important open problems in regulatory informatics. It is part of the research agenda that the HARNESS project is designed to address.

The regulatory framework creates a layered ecosystem of named technical roles, each corresponding to a defined set of obligations and a corresponding set of technical artefacts. These roles are not static: they are triggered, modified, and potentially transferred by engineering decisions, deployment configurations, and system modifications. Compliance architecture must therefore be designed around the organisation's full role topology — provider/deployer (AI Act), controller/processor (GDPR), data holder/user/intermediary (Data Act/DGA), manufacturer/importer (CRA), essential/important entity (NIS2) — and that topology must be maintained as a living artefact that is updated whenever a system change, business change, or regulatory change alters the role allocation.

Discharging the obligations attached to each role increasingly requires machine-readable representation, not merely written policy. The vocabulary ecosystem surveyed in Section 7.6 — DPV, ODRL, Croissant, AIRO/VAIR/TAIR, AICat, LegalRuleML, SHACL, and DCAT-AP/MLDCAT-AP — provides substantial, if fragmented, coverage of this representational need. The absence of an integrated, cross-regulation compliance substrate is itself one of the central findings of this chapter, and it is the bridge to Chapter 8, which turns from role and representation analysis to the broader tooling landscape, the enforcement gaps that persist even where representation is adequate, and the compliance-tool ecosystem examined against the backdrop of the obligations and roles identified here.

8 MAPPING REGULATIONS TO INFORMATICS TOOLS AND METHODS

This chapter maps the regulatory analysis of Chapters 4–7 to the compliance tooling landscape surveyed in Deliverable D2.2, identifies the gaps between regulatory intent and current technical capability, and articulates the open research challenges that remain for the informatics community. Its organising claim is that tooling coverage across the EU regulatory framework is structurally uneven: the GDPR has accumulated a relatively mature compliance-tool ecosystem over more than seven years of operation; AI Act tooling is nascent; and Data Act and DGA tooling remains thin. The most significant implementability gaps — meaningful explainability for deep learning models, machine unlearning under GDPR Article 17, cryptographically enforced purpose limitation in federated data spaces, meaningful human oversight under AI Act Article 14, and adversarial-testing certification for GPAI models with systemic risk — are not merely engineering problems awaiting better software; they constitute open research problems for the informatics community.

8.1 From Requirements to Compliance Tools

The regulatory obligations catalogued in earlier chapters can be mapped to families of compliance tooling, although the maturity of each family varies dramatically.

8.1.1 Data Flow, Purpose Limitation, and Lawful Basis

GDPR purpose-limitation and data-flow obligations are addressed by data lineage and provenance tools, GDPR-specific compliance frameworks, and ontology-based reasoning systems. The CLAUDETTE project (Lippi et al. 2019) applies machine learning and NLP to detect potentially unfair clauses in online platforms' terms of service — a paradigm case for automated regulatory analysis, published in *Artificial Intelligence and Law* 27(2):117–139. GDPRov and GDPRtEXT (Pandit et al., 2018, 2018b) provide semantic-web ontologies extending PROV-O and SKOS to model data and consent lifecycles and to expose the GDPR text itself as machine-readable linked data, published at the 15th Extended Semantic Web Conference. The W3C Data Privacy Vocabulary (Esteves et al., 2026) extends this line of work into a community-standard vocabulary for processing operations, lawful bases, technical and organisational measures, and rights, providing the metadata substrate for interoperable compliance tooling.

8.1.2 Consent Management

Consent under GDPR Articles 6(1)(a), 7, and 9(2)(a) is addressed by consent management platforms (CMPs). Industry-standard CMPs handle cookie consent, preference centres, and granular purpose-by-purpose toggles, typically built on the IAB Europe Transparency and Consent Framework (TCF). A substantial body of empirical research documents that CMPs as deployed are systematically non-compliant in practice. Matte, Santos, and Bielova (2020) established 17 fine-grained legal requirements for compliant cookie banners derived from joint legal and technical analysis, finding widespread non-compliance across deployed implementations. Toth, Bielova, and Roca (2022) demonstrated that CMPs themselves manipulate website publishers into non-compliant configurations through dark patterns embedded in CMP configuration interfaces. Gray et al. (2021) analysed the structural conflict between the legal requirements for consent and the interface designs CMPs produce, finding that dark patterns — asymmetric accept/reject button prominence, buried opt-out paths, and misleading framing — are not incidental but incentive-driven. Most recently, Kancherla et al (PETS, 2025) measured consent revocation specifically, finding that 49% of the top-200 websites offer non-compliant revocation interfaces, 57.5% do not delete cookies after revocation, and 2.48% provide no revocation mechanism at all. The pattern across this literature is consistent: CMPs as deployed frequently satisfy the surface form of GDPR Articles 6(1)(a) and 7 without satisfying their substance. The downstream consequence for AI systems is particularly acute: a user who has withdrawn consent may remain in training data that was lawfully collected at the time but whose continued use now lacks a valid lawful basis, and the propagation of consent withdrawal signals through data warehouse and ML pipeline infrastructure is a technical problem that the CMP layer does not address.

8.1.3 High-Risk AI System Requirements

The AI Act's high-risk system regime is addressed by AI auditing frameworks and documentation tools. ALTAI — the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI published by the AI HLEG on 17 July 2020 — provides a voluntary self-assessment instrument covering seven requirement areas: human agency and oversight; technical robustness and safety; privacy and data governance; transparency; diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness; environmental and societal well-being; and accountability (AI HLEG, 2020). Z-Inspection® (Zicari et al., 2021) provides a process-based, evidence-driven multidisciplinary audit framework operationalising the HLEG requirements through a claim–argument–evidence structure.

Model cards (Mitchell et al., 2019) and datasheets for datasets (Gebru et al., 2021) provide documentation templates that map closely onto AI Act Annex IV technical documentation requirements. AIF360 (Bellamy et al., 2018) is a tool that can address AI Act Article 10 bias-mitigation obligations through a library of fairness metrics and bias-mitigation algorithms including reweighting, adversarial debiasing, and reject-option classification. Post-hoc explainability tools — SHAP (Lundberg and Lee, 2017) and LIME (Ribeiro et al., 2016) — can help address AI Act Article 13 transparency obligations at the level of feature attribution.

8.1.4 Cybersecurity Compliance

Cybersecurity obligations under NIS2, the CRA, and DORA are addressed by a mature but fragmented tooling landscape. SIEM platforms (Splunk, Microsoft Sentinel, IBM QRadar) address NIS2 Article 21 incident-detection obligations, providing rule-based alerting and automated incident classification. EDR tools address the real-time telemetry requirements for the four-hour DORA incident-notification window. SBOM tooling — Syft, cdxgen, SPDX-tools, CycloneDX — addresses the CRA Annex I Part II SBOM obligation. Vulnerability-management platforms (Tenable, Qualys) address CRA Article 14 actively-exploited-vulnerability-reporting obligations. DAST and SAST tools address CRA Annex I Part I security-by-design obligations during the software development lifecycle.

8.1.5 Data-Space Compliance

The Data Act and DGA data-space obligations are addressed, imperfectly, by IDS Connector implementations and ODRL-based policy engines (such as LUCON, MYDATA, and D°). These operationalise the IDS Usage Control Language, but the ecosystem remains fragmented: interoperability between connectors from different IDS-certified vendors is not yet seamless, and no comprehensive Data-Act-specific compliance suite is generally available. ODRL-based usage control is a declarative specification of what should happen in a data-sharing interaction; it does not provide cryptographic guarantees that it will happen, as discussed in Section 8.2.

The coverage across these families is highly uneven. GDPR has the deepest tooling ecosystem, accumulated over more than seven years of operational practice. AI Act tooling is nascent: the GPAI Code of Practice was published only in July 2025, harmonised standards under CEN/CENELEC are still under development, and Annex IV technical-documentation templates remain to be

operationalised through implementing acts. Data Act and DGA tooling is the least developed of the families considered. The detailed survey in Deliverable D2.2 catalogues these tools and their coverage gaps; the present chapter provides the regulatory mapping to which that survey is the technical counterpart.

8.2 Gaps Between Regulatory Intent and Technical Implementability

Several gaps between regulatory requirements and current technical capability are sufficiently severe to constitute an *implementability gap*: a structural discrepancy between what the law demands and what the technology can, at present, deliver.

8.2.1 The Explainability Gap

AI Act Article 13(1) requires that high-risk AI systems be designed and developed "in such a way as to ensure that their operation is sufficiently transparent to enable deployers to interpret the system's output and use it appropriately". Article 86 confers on affected persons a right to obtain "clear and meaningful explanations of the role of the AI system in the decision-making procedure". Current explainability methods are predominantly post-hoc approximations rather than ground-truth explanations.

SHAP (Lundberg and Lee, 2017) provides game-theoretic feature attributions with mathematical consistency guarantees but assumes additive feature contributions that may not hold for deep networks. LIME (Ribeiro et al., 2016) provides locally faithful linear approximations, but its stability is empirically limited: Burger et al. (2023) report explanation-similarity drops of approximately 16–28.5% across three text-classifier benchmarks when sampling rates vary. Attention maps in transformers are routinely used as proxies for "what the model attended to", but the correspondence between attention weights and causal influence on the output is empirically weak. The gap between Article 13's "meaningful explanation" and the actual epistemic content of post-hoc explanations is the most visible gap in the current AI Act tooling landscape. Counterfactual explanations — "change X to obtain outcome Y" — are arguably more legally meaningful because they are operationally actionable, but remain underused in production systems.

8.2.2 Data Erasure in Trained Models

GDPR Article 17 confers a right to erasure. Whether and to what extent that right extends to personal data used to train a machine learning model remains contested. ML researchers commonly interpret Article 17 as applying both to the training dataset and to the trained model itself (Juliussen et al., 2023). Wholesale retraining of a large model in response to a single individual's deletion request is computationally and economically prohibitive for state-of-the-art systems. Machine unlearning — removing the influence of specific data points from a trained model without full retraining — is the field of ML research that seeks to address this. The literature is now substantial, covering gradient-based unlearning, influence-function-based approaches, certified removal under restrictive convexity assumptions, and SISA-style partition-and-retrain approaches, but the

techniques remain either approximate or expensive, and none provides the kind of "removal" that a strict reading of Article 17 would require for generative models (Cooper et al., 2024).

8.2.3 Purpose Limitation in Federated Data Spaces

GDPR Article 5(1)(b) requires that personal data be collected for "specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes". In a federated data-sharing environment — a Common European Data Space, an EHDS Health Data Access Body environment, an IDS data space — the data leaves the controller's enforcement perimeter once it is shared with a recipient. As Steinbuß et al. (2021) acknowledge in the IDSA Position Paper on Usage Control, enforcement of usage policies "only works if the respective mechanisms are installed on the data consumer side". ODRL and the IDS Usage Control Language are declarative specifications of what *should* happen, not cryptographic guarantees of what *will* happen. Side-channel exfiltration, screen capture, and out-of-band copying are not preventable through usage control. Confidential-computing primitives (Intel SGX, AMD SEV-SNP, ARM CCA) offer partial mitigations through hardware-enforced isolation, but their threat models do not cover all leakage paths and their adoption in data-space deployments is still limited. The technical state of the art cannot yet deliver enforceable purpose limitation across the participant boundary.

8.spdx Meaningful Human Oversight

AI Act Article 14(4) requires that the natural persons assigned human oversight of a high-risk AI system be enabled, as appropriate to the circumstances, to "properly understand the relevant capacities and limitations of the high-risk AI system and be able to duly monitor its operation", and to "remain aware of the possible tendency of automatically relying or over-relying on the output". For complex deep-learning systems — large language models, multimodal vision–language systems, agentic AI systems with tool use — this requirement is aspirationally stated and technically unresolved. The foundational literature on automation bias is clear: Skitka, Mosier, and Burdick (1999), in their seminal study demonstrated systematic over-reliance even where participants were instructed to evaluate automated outputs critically. More recent work by Vered et al. (2023) finds that providing explanations "did not reduce this aspect of automation bias and sometimes increased it" (*ScienceDirect*, 2023). The AI Act provides no quantitative benchmark — no minimum override rate, no maximum decision latency, no required level of comprehension. Organisations are left to determine these parameters themselves, and supervisory authorities will need to develop interpretive practice over time.

8.2.5 Recommender System Transparency

DSA Article 27(1) requires providers of recommender systems to set out the main parameters used in their recommender systems in plain and intelligible language. For modern deep-learning recommender architectures — two-tower retrieval models, sequence transformers, graph neural networks over user–item interaction graphs — there is no tractable technical representation of "why" a recommendation was made that is simultaneously truthful and intelligible to a non-expert recipient. Platforms have responded with high-level natural-language descriptions that are

intelligible but partial, or with feature-importance-style explanations that are precise but unintelligible to lay audiences. The Article 27 obligation thus operates at a level of abstraction where technical correctness and lay intelligibility are in structural tension that current tooling cannot fully resolve.

8.2.6 Audit and Certification for GPAI Models

AI Act Article 55(1)(a) requires providers of GPAI models with systemic risk to perform model evaluation "in accordance with standardised protocols and tools reflecting the state of the art, including conducting and documenting adversarial testing of the model with a view to identifying and mitigating systemic risks". The GPAI Code of Practice, Chapter 3 (Safety and Security), operationalises this through a Safety and Security Framework requirement. However, red-teaming methodologies are not yet standardised, there is no agreed taxonomy of systemic risks, coverage guarantees are impossible for general-purpose systems by construction, and the external evaluation ecosystem is immature. The Commission's own Guidelines on GPAI obligations acknowledge the immature state of external evaluation ecosystems and indicate that the AI Office may coordinate development of consistent standards. For technical practitioners, compliance with Article 55(1)(a) currently requires substantial judgment exercised under uncertainty, not the application of a settled methodology.

8.3 Open Challenges for the Research Community

The implementability gaps catalogued in Section 8.2 translate into a research agenda for the informatics community. Seven problems stand out.

Formal verification of neural networks at scale. Current neural-network verification tools — α , β -CROWN, Marabou, ERAN, and successors — handle small to medium networks for narrow properties such as local robustness around specified input regions. State-of-the-art research (Kuper et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2020; Baninajjar et al., 2023) has extended scalability through pruning, abstraction-refinement, and GPU acceleration, but production large language models remain orders of magnitude beyond reach. Bridging this gap will require either fundamentally new abstraction techniques, verification-friendly training regimes, or modular verification that decomposes large systems into separately verifiable subcomponents.

Machine unlearning. Despite a rapidly expanding literature, there is no efficient, verifiable, model-agnostic unlearning method that preserves model utility. Open problems include rigorous definitions of unlearning that capture what GDPR Article 17 actually demands; verification protocols allowing a data subject or supervisory authority to verify that personal data has been "forgotten"; and unlearning for foundation models where the contribution of an individual data point is highly distributed across millions of parameters (Liu et al., 2024; Juliussen et al., 2023).

Cross-regulatory compliance checking. No existing tool or framework provides integrated compliance checking across multiple EU regulations simultaneously. The interactions catalogued in

Chapter 6 — GDPR/NIS2 retention conflicts, AI Act/CRA conformity overlaps, DORA/NIS2 incident-reporting timeline divergence — are not addressed by any current tooling at the level required to support engineering decision-making. A research agenda here would combine semantic-web representations of obligations (extending DPV, GDPRtEXT, and emerging AI-Act ontologies) with formal reasoning over the obligation graph, producing a cross-regulatory compliance reasoner that can identify conflicts and flag unresolved tensions.

Continuous compliance monitoring. Regulations now require ongoing compliance, not point-in-time conformity. AI Act post-market monitoring (Article 72), NIS2 continuous incident detection (Article 21), DORA continuous ICT monitoring (Article 13), and CRA lifecycle vulnerability handling (Annex I Part II) collectively demand automated, continuous compliance monitoring infrastructure. Today's compliance dashboards are point-in-time snapshots; the open problem is building telemetry pipelines that produce continuous compliance evidence with the integrity and verifiability that supervisory authorities require.

Regulatory NLP and automated norm extraction. Automatically extracting machine-readable obligations from legal text remains imprecise. Rule-based approaches (CLAUDETTE-style) achieve high precision on narrow domains but limited recall. LLM-based approaches improve recall and generalisation but introduce hallucination risks that are unacceptable in a compliance context. A productive line of research combines LLM-based extraction with formal verification against authoritative legal sources (EUR-Lex, EDPB guidelines), using hallucination-resistant retrieval-augmented architectures to constrain the model's outputs to verifiable regulatory text.

Data-space compliance. Enforcing regulatory obligations — purpose limitation, access rights, data-quality requirements — in federated data spaces with heterogeneous participants is an open engineering and research challenge. The current technical baseline (IDS Connector with ODRL-based usage control) lacks cryptographic enforcement guarantees and does not yet integrate cleanly with GDPR rights mechanisms (subject access, rectification, erasure). Research directions include the application of confidential-computing primitives, zero-knowledge-proof-based access auditing, and federated-learning architectures that minimise data movement.

Quantifying the implementability gap. Finally, and at a meta level, there is no systematic framework for measuring how far current technical capabilities fall short of regulatory requirements. Each of the gaps discussed in Section 8.2 is described qualitatively; none is yet quantified by an agreed methodology. The development of such a framework — combining controlled benchmarks, capability evaluations, and structured assessment of regulatory satisfiability — would itself be a significant contribution to the field, allowing regulators and engineers alike to understand where compliance is achievable, where it is currently impossible, and where targeted research investment could close the gap.

8.4 Recommendations for Practice

For the HARNES consortium and its target audience of engineers, data architects, and AI developers, the analysis above yields a set of staged, concrete next steps. These are addressed primarily to organisations developing or deploying AI systems, data-space participants, and operators of critical infrastructure, and not to the research consortium itself, which engages with these obligations analytically rather than operationally.

Immediate (now to August 2026). Map the organisation's role topology across each instrument in scope and document it in a single, version-controlled artefact that is updated on every system change. Establish a unified incident-response procedure that triggers DORA's four-hour, NIS2's 24-hour, and GDPR's 72-hour clocks simultaneously, with classification logic that determines which obligations apply. Architect logging so that personal-data minimisation and forensic integrity are reconciled by design rather than retrofitted. Adopt model cards, datasheets, and DPV-based metadata as a baseline documentation substrate; sign on to the GPAI Code of Practice if developing or fine-tuning GPAI models.

Medium term (12 to 24 months). Invest in pipeline-integrated SBOM tooling (CycloneDX or SPDX with cdxgen or Syft); integrate fairness evaluation (AIF360 or equivalents) and explainability (SHAP, Lundberg and Lee, 2017, and LIME, Ribeiro et al., 2016) with documented stability bounds, plus counterfactual explanations for user-facing decisions) into MLOps pipelines as first-class artefacts. Begin participation in IDS-aligned data-space initiatives if cross-organisational data sharing is in scope. Pre-position contractual templates for AI Act Article 25 cooperation, particularly for organisations that may be reclassified as providers through substantial modification.

Long term (24 months and beyond). Contribute to the open research agenda set out in Section 8.3 — formal verification, machine unlearning, cross-regulatory reasoning, continuous compliance monitoring. Track the legislative trajectory of the Digital Omnibus closely; the threshold that would substantively change compliance architecture is the formal adoption of the omnibus regulations and the publication of associated implementing acts. Where the organisation operates in multiple Member States, develop per-jurisdiction rule layers that can be updated independently as transposition and case law evolve.

8.5 Caveats

Several caveats merit explicit statement. First, the Digital Omnibus proposals discussed throughout are at the time of writing still in the legislative process: the AI component was provisionally agreed on 7 May 2026 but is not yet formally adopted; the GDPR, Data Act, and NIS2 components are still under negotiation. Engineering decisions taken on the assumption that omnibus changes will pass in their current form should be hedged.

Second, EDPB Opinion 28/2024, while highly influential, uses heavily qualified language and explicitly contemplates case-by-case national interpretation. Cross-jurisdictional uniformity should not be assumed; engineering choices in one Member State may not satisfy supervisors in another.

Third, several quantitative figures cited in the literature — the eighteen-month NIS2 log-retention horizon, the 3–10× telemetry cost multiplier, the €5M–€15M annual GPAI systemic-risk compliance cost — originate from industry rather than peer-reviewed academic sources and should be treated as orders of magnitude rather than precise estimates.

Fourth, harmonised technical standards under the AI Act (CEN/CENELEC) and the CRA are still under development. Several obligations analysed here — notably AI Act Article 14 human oversight and Article 55 GPAI evaluation — will be operationally refined when standards are adopted, and present analyses should be revisited at that point.

Fifth, the cross-references to Deliverable D2.2 in this chapter require integration with that document's final text; citation markers should be resolved before publication.

The regulatory framework imposes a set of compliance obligations that the current tooling landscape can address, partially and unevenly, for GDPR and partially for the AI Act, but that remain substantially unaddressed for the Data Act, DGA, and for the cross-regulatory integration problem. The implementability gaps identified in Section 8.2 are not merely the teething problems of a new regulatory framework; they are structurally rooted in the state of the underlying science and engineering disciplines. Addressing them will require sustained research investment in formal verification, machine unlearning, privacy-preserving computation, and cross-regulatory reasoning — areas that constitute a core part of the HARNES project's research agenda.

9 CASE STUDIES

The preceding chapters have analysed the EU AI and data regulatory framework at the level of instruments, clusters, role-obligation mappings, and machine-readable representations. This chapter shifts to the level of concrete deployment contexts, tracing how the framework bears on engineers and organisations operating in four domains: AI systems in high-risk sectors, data spaces governed by the Data Act and EHDS, cybersecurity compliance in critical infrastructure, and AI systems in education. These are not exhaustive case studies of specific products or organisations; they are structured composite scenarios derived from the regulatory analysis, designed to illustrate how the constraint satisfaction problem the framework creates is experienced in practice.

9.1 AI Systems in High-Risk Sectors

9.1.1. Healthcare: AI-assisted diagnosis in a hospital

Consider a hospital that deploys an AI system for radiological image analysis — classifying findings in chest X-rays to assist clinicians in prioritising cases. The system was acquired from a commercial provider and is used under the hospital's authority by radiologists and clinical staff.

The AI Act classifies AI systems intended to be used for diagnosis of disease as high-risk under Annex III, point 5(a). As a deployer of a high-risk AI system, the hospital must: use the system in accordance with the provider's instructions for use (Article 26(1)); ensure that human oversight is performed by radiologists with the competence and authority to disregard or override the system's outputs (Article 26(2)); monitor operation and report serious incidents and malfunctions to the provider and, where applicable, to the relevant market surveillance authority (Articles 26(5) and 73); and — as a body governed by public law — conduct a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment before first operational use (Article 27).

The hospital is simultaneously a GDPR controller for patient imaging data processed by the system. It must document the AI processing activity in its Article 30 records of processing activities, conduct a DPIA under Article 35 (high-risk processing involving health data is mandatory), and establish a lawful basis for the processing — in this context likely Article 9(2)(h) (health care) combined with Article 6(1)(c) (legal obligation) or 6(1)(e) (public task). The EHDS Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2025/327) adds obligations for the electronic health records that feed the AI system: the hospital must ensure those records conform to EHDS interoperability standards, specifically HL7 FHIR profiles for relevant data categories, and must implement access controls aligned with the EHDS primary-use access framework.

Under NIS2, the hospital — as an entity in the health sector — is an essential entity subject to Article 21 security obligations and Article 23 incident reporting. An AI system failure that constitutes a significant incident must be reported to the national CSIRT within 24 hours of awareness, in addition to the AI Act's market surveillance notification. The hospital must therefore maintain incident classification playbooks that correctly identify when an AI malfunction crosses the NIS2 "significant incident" threshold and simultaneously triggers the AI Act serious-incident reporting pathway and the GDPR breach-notification obligation if patient data is compromised.

If the AI system components also qualify as medical devices under MDR — a contested boundary for clinical decision support software — the hospital as a health institution using the device would not itself be an MDR manufacturer, but it must ensure the provider holds a valid CE marking under MDR and must participate in the post-market surveillance data feedback loop under MDR Article 83.

The documentation stack the hospital must maintain includes: AI Act Annex IV technical documentation (or access to it from the provider), Article 30 ROPA entry, DPIA, FRIA, EHDS access control records, NIS2 incident response procedures, and — for the imaging pipeline — FHIR conformance documentation (Mantelero, 2024). For practical management, these artefacts should be maintained as a cross-referenced documentation graph, with each artefact linked to the others and to the regulatory provisions it addresses. The DPV, AI Cards, and DCAT-based tools described in Chapter 9 provide partial implementations of this graph; no integrated tooling covers the full multi-regulation documentation requirement.

9.1.2 Financial services: AI-driven credit scoring

A credit institution deploys an AI system for automated credit-scoring assessments of retail loan applications. Credit or loan applications and assessments are explicitly listed in AI Act Annex III, point 5(b) as a high-risk use case. The institution is simultaneously subject to GDPR, DORA, NIS2, and — as a financial entity — to the specific requirements of DORA as a *lex specialis* displacing NIS2 where the two overlap.

As a deployer of a high-risk AI system, the institution must implement the Article 26 deployer obligations described above. If it has fine-tuned or substantially modified the model, it may have been reclassified as a provider under Article 25 and must then satisfy the full provider obligation set including conformity assessment before market placement. The credit-scoring decision implicates GDPR Article 22, which restricts solely automated decisions that produce legal or similarly significant effects on individuals: the institution must ensure that a human reviewer is meaningfully involved in final decisions, or rely on one of the Article 22 exceptions (necessity for entering a contract, explicit consent, or authorisation by law) and implement safeguards including the right of explanation and the right to contest. AI Act Article 14 human oversight obligations are consistent with Article 22's requirements but not coextensive: Article 14 applies to the AI system's operational context regardless of whether the decision is "solely automated," while Article 22 is triggered specifically when meaningful human involvement is absent.

DORA's ICT risk management framework (Articles 5–15) requires the institution to include the AI credit-scoring system in its ICT risk register, conduct regular testing including vulnerability assessments, and manage the AI system provider as a critical ICT third-party service provider under Articles 28–44 if the provider is classified as such by the ESAs. The DORA-specific four-hour major-incident reporting obligation runs parallel to GDPR's 72-hour breach notification and to the AI Act's serious-incident reporting; the institution must maintain unified incident-response procedures that simultaneously trigger all three clocks with correct classification logic.

The credit-scoring context also illustrates the AI Act's data representativeness requirement most acutely. The model must perform consistently across relevant population subgroups — age, sex, racial or ethnic origin — to satisfy Article 10(3) and Article 15's non-discrimination accuracy requirements. Achieving this requires demographic data on applicants, which is restricted under GDPR Article 9 (special categories) in many Member States. AI Act Article 10(5) permits processing of special categories for bias detection in high-risk AI systems, but the precise scope of this permission and its interaction with Member State law implementing GDPR Article 9(4) varies. The EDPB's Opinion 28/2024 case-by-case approach provides no definitive answer; the institution must make a documented legal assessment for its specific national context.

9.2 Data Spaces Under the Data Act and EHDS

9.2.1 Industrial IoT data space

A manufacturing consortium establishes a cross-company data space to share production data generated by connected industrial machinery, enabling predictive maintenance, efficiency benchmarking, and supply-chain coordination. The technical implementation uses IDS Connectors operating under the IDSA Dataspace Protocol, with ODRL-based usage control policies attached to data assets at the point of sharing.

Under the Data Act (applicable from September 2025), the manufacturers — as data holders whose connected products generate the shared data — must provide users access to the data in real time and facilitate user-directed third-party sharing under Articles 4 and 5. Where the data includes personal data of workers (shift identifiers, performance metrics embedded in production logs), the data holder must separate or pseudonymise that data before sharing to comply with GDPR Article 5(1)(b) purpose limitation — the workers consented to the original collection for employment purposes, not for supply-chain optimisation. The engineering challenge is building data pipelines that identify and transform personal data fields in real-time telemetry streams before they reach the connector, preserving the analytical utility of the dataset while eliminating the GDPR exposure.

The DGA classifies the consortium's shared data infrastructure as a data-sharing service subject to data intermediary requirements under Chapter II, if it provides commercial services for data sharing between participants. Compliance requires functional separation of the data-sharing service from any other commercial activities, strict neutrality regarding participants, and notification to the national competent authority. The IDSA Connector architecture is aligned with these requirements but formal DGA compliance requires documented governance structures — intermediary agreements, purpose-limitation policies, audit logging — that the technical infrastructure alone does not guarantee.

Usage control enforcement illustrates the gap between regulatory intent and technical reality. ODRL policies attached to data assets can express that data must be deleted after 90 days, must not be used to derive competing products, or must be processed only in anonymised form. But connector operators cannot verify that downstream data consumers honour these obligations after data transfer. Confidential computing solutions — where data processing occurs in hardware-attested trusted execution environments that the data owner can verify — provide a partial mitigation but are not yet mainstream in industrial IoT contexts and impose performance overhead. The data space therefore operates on a combination of technical controls (access restrictions at the connector level) and contractual enforcement (intermediary agreements with audit rights and penalty clauses), accepting that full technical enforcement of purpose limitation is not achievable with current tools.

9.2.2 EHDS secondary-use data space

Under the EHDS Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2025/327), each Member State must establish a Health Data Access Body (HDAB) that processes secondary-use requests from researchers, public authorities, and industry. Researchers wishing to access pseudonymised patient data for a clinical study submit a data permit application to the relevant HDAB; if granted, they access the data within a ring-fenced secure processing environment.

The HDAB operates at the intersection of four regulatory regimes. GDPR requires that data processing in the secure environment respect purpose limitation, data minimisation, and the original collection purposes; the EHDS provides an additional legal basis in Article 60 for secondary use under the data permit, but this basis is subject to Member State restrictions on certain categories of secondary use. AI systems used to analyse the health data — for example, a machine-learning model trained on the permitted dataset — must satisfy AI Act Article 10 data governance requirements and, if the model is subsequently deployed in a clinical context, the relevant Annex III high-risk provisions. MDR may apply if the model output constitutes clinical decision support in the technical sense of the Medical Device Regulation. The EHDS data quality framework and HL7 FHIR profiles govern the format of data made available through the HDAB; researchers must ensure their analysis pipelines are compatible with these formats and must document dataset characteristics in a manner consistent with AI Act Annex IV requirements if a model will be placed on the market.

The documentation obligations for a researcher accessing EHDS data for ML model development are therefore: a data permit from the HDAB (EHDS), a data processing agreement with the HDAB acting as controller (GDPR), a DPIA if the research involves high-risk processing (GDPR Article 35), Croissant or MLDCAT-AP dataset documentation (AI Act Article 10 and Annex IV if the model is intended for deployment), model cards and AI Cards documentation (AI Act Articles 11 and 13), and conformity assessment under AI Act Article 43 if the resulting model is classified as high-risk and placed on the EU market. The identification and management of this documentation stack is a practical challenge that the HARNES compliance tooling research agenda is designed to address.

9.3 Cybersecurity Compliance in Critical Infrastructure

9.3.1 Energy sector operator

A national electricity grid operator is an essential entity under NIS2 by virtue of its presence in Annex I's energy sector. It operates industrial control systems and SCADA infrastructure that are products with digital elements and therefore also fall within the CRA's scope when commercial components are procured or when in-house software is commercially distributed. An AI system for predictive anomaly detection on grid sensors is deployed as an auxiliary decision-support tool for control room operators.

The operator's NIS2 Article 21 obligations are comprehensive: risk analysis, incident handling, business continuity, supply-chain security (covering the AI anomaly-detection vendor), security in system acquisition and maintenance (covering the AI system's update and patching lifecycle), vulnerability handling (requiring coordination with the AI vendor's vulnerability disclosure programme), multi-factor authentication for all control room access, and mandatory encryption for sensitive operational data. The Article 23 three-stage incident reporting regime applies to significant incidents, with the 24-hour early warning to the national CSIRT being the most operationally demanding timeline.

The CRA applies to products with digital elements that the operator procures from commercial vendors. Before September 2026, the operator must verify that newly procured control system components and AI-adjacent software carry CE marking under the CRA or are in the process of obtaining it, and must implement a supplier-management process that tracks CRA compliance status across its software supply chain. SBOM documentation from vendors — in CycloneDX or SPDX format, per BSI TR-03183-2 guidance — must be ingested into the operator's vulnerability management process, with automated scanning against known vulnerability databases.

The AI anomaly-detection system sits at the intersection of the AI Act and CRA. It is not itself a high-risk AI system under Annex III (which does not list grid anomaly detection), though if it were to take automated control actions — rather than supporting human decision-making — the classification might change. As a product with digital elements, it must comply with CRA Annex I Part I essential cybersecurity requirements if commercially procured. If the operator has developed the system in-house for its own use without commercial distribution, the CRA's manufacturer obligations may not apply, but NIS2 Article 21 obligations for the security of the system remain in full force.

The interaction between the AI system's human oversight requirement under AI Act Article 14 and the operator's SCADA operational procedures illustrates the automation-bias problem discussed in Chapter 10. Control room operators trained to rely on automated anomaly detection may fail to critically evaluate alerts, potentially increasing the probability of both false-positive response (unnecessary grid intervention) and false-negative oversight (missed genuine anomaly). The operator must design training procedures, interface ergonomics, and override protocols that mitigate this risk, documented as part of the deployer obligations under AI Act Article 26, but without regulatory guidance on what constitutes an adequate mitigation strategy.

9.4 AI Systems in Education

The education sector has emerged as one of the most complex deployment environments for AI systems, combining Annex III high-risk classification for AI in educational assessment with the particular sensitivities of processing data about minors, the public-sector obligations of state educational institutions, and the rapid adoption of generative AI tools across academic contexts.

9.4.1 AI-assisted student assessment

An AI system used by a national examinations authority to assist in the grading of written assessments — comparing student answers against model answers, flagging potential misconduct, and recommending grades for human reviewer confirmation — falls within AI Act Annex III, point 3(a) (AI systems used for decisions on access to educational institutions or for evaluating students). As a deployer of a high-risk AI system that is a body governed by public law, the examinations authority must conduct a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment before first use (Article 27) in addition to the standard Article 26 deployer obligations.

Students whose assessments are processed by the AI system are data subjects under the GDPR; many are minors under 18. GDPR Article 22 applies if the assessment outcome is determined (or

substantively influenced) by solely automated processing; human reviewer confirmation is required, but the design of that review must ensure meaningful human agency rather than rubber-stamping of the AI recommendation. EDPB guidance on Article 22 in educational contexts indicates that the automated tool's output should be one input to a holistic assessment, not the primary determinant.

The examinations authority is likely an essential entity under NIS2 if it operates digital assessment infrastructure at scale, triggering the full Article 21 security obligation set. Assessment data — which includes detailed student academic performance profiles — constitutes personal data requiring GDPR-grade protection; any security incident affecting assessment integrity or data confidentiality triggers both the NIS2 Article 23 incident reporting and the GDPR Article 33 breach notification obligations.

9.4.2 Generative AI in higher education

The deployment of general-purpose AI tools — large language model-based writing assistance, automated literature review, research question generation — in university settings raises a distinct set of regulatory questions. The tools themselves are GPAI models under AI Act Articles 51–55; their providers must comply with the GPAI transparency obligations (Article 53) and, if systemic-risk models, the Article 55 enhanced obligations. The university deploying those tools under institutional licences is a deployer with Article 26 obligations.

Students using the tools are data subjects; where usage involves processing of personal data (student identifiers associated with prompts, academic content that could identify individuals), GDPR obligations apply to the institution as controller. The ePrivacy Directive applies to any tracking of student usage on institutional networks. The Interoperable Europe Act applies if the university is implementing cross-border digital public services for student data exchange.

The academic research exemption in AI Act Article 2(8) exempts GPAI models "developed and put into service for the sole purpose of scientific research and development" from the GPAI provisions, but the boundary between in-scope research use and out-of-scope research is not clearly drawn for university projects that develop models with potential commercial or public-interest applications. Research groups producing open-source models that are subsequently adopted by downstream users may find themselves in the provider role without having intended to occupy it — a gap in the regulatory framework that has received attention in academic commentary but has not yet been resolved by supervisory authority guidance.

The education case study therefore illustrates both the framework's reach — it extends deep into institutions that may not historically have thought of themselves as AI system deployers in a regulatory sense — and a structural gap in the framework's risk classification logic: the potential harms of AI in educational assessment (discrimination, breach of academic integrity, chilling of creative academic work) are significant, but the compliance architecture for detecting and remedying those harms at the level of individual students remains underdeveloped relative to the documentation and risk management obligations it imposes on institutions.

10 CONCLUSION

This deliverable set out to read the EU's AI and data regulatory framework as an engineer rather than a lawyer would: not asking what the law says, but what it requires a technical system to do. Across the regulatory landscape, the standards that bridge it to implementation, the interactions and tensions that arise when instruments are applied together, the roles and obligations each instrument creates, and the tooling available to discharge them, a consistent pattern emerges. The framework is coherent in its individual parts and considerably harder to satisfy as a whole: obligations that are each well-specified in isolation routinely conflict, overlap, or leave gaps once a real system must satisfy several of them at once, and the compliance-tooling and machine-readable-vocabulary ecosystems that exist to help, while substantial, remain fragmented across instruments rather than integrated across them. The case studies in Chapter 9 show this is not a theoretical concern; it is the everyday condition of building AI and data systems for healthcare, finance, critical infrastructure, and education in the EU today.

The practical value of this analysis lies less in any single finding than in its use as a structured reference point: a map that engineers, data architects, and researchers can consult to identify which obligations apply to a given system, which standards and tools exist to meet them, and where the current state of the art does not yet reach. The accompanying mapping tables are designed for direct reuse in compliance tooling and ontology development elsewhere in the project. Future work should extend the analysis along three lines: the Digital Omnibus package, provisionally agreed for its AI Act component in May 2026 but still in legislative process for its GDPR, Data Act, and NIS2 components, will require revision of several chapters once adopted; the implementability gaps identified in Chapter 8 — particularly machine unlearning, cross-regulatory compliance reasoning, and continuous compliance monitoring — constitute a concrete research agenda; and building the integrated, cross-regulation machine-readable compliance profile that Chapter 7 shows does not yet exist remains one of the most consequential open problems this deliverable surfaces. All three are work the HARNES project is positioned to take forward, including through the deeper, article-specific semantic modelling already under way in D2.4 and the legal knowledge formalisation framework developed in D1.4.

DECLARATION OF USE OF AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES

The authors used Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies, Anthropic's Claude Sonnet, Claude Opus, and Claude Fable, for language assistance such as spelling and grammar checking, and for editing the form of this manuscript with no additions to its content. All technical content, experimental results, and scientific claims were verified and are the responsibility of the authors.

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